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Slurry Store

Experimental and numerical investigations of ice slurry
storages

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The author of this report bears the entire responsibility for the content and for the conclusions drawn therefrom.

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List of Acronyms

ASHP	Air Source Heat Pump
BCF	Burton-Cabrera-Frank Model
CNT	Classical nucleation theory
EPDM	Ethylene propylene diene monomer rubber
FI	Flow indicator
GSHP	Ground Source Heat Pump
IBC	intermediate bulk container
IPF	Ice packing factor
MFH	Multi Family Home
PHX	Plate heat exchanger
STI	Slurry Tank Inlet
TI	Temperature indicator
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
US	ultrasonic

Glossary

Notation	Description	Page List
<i>barrier</i>	device used to prevent upstream propagation.	24, 29
<i>Burton-Cabrera-Frank</i>	a continuous crystal growth model in which the dislocations of existing crystals are the source of further growth.	24
<i>cavitation</i>	process, in which the static pressure of a liquid is temporarily reduced to below the liquid's vapor pressure, leading to the formation of small vapor-filled cavities in the liquid. When subjected to higher pressure again, these cavities, called "bubbles" or "voids", collapse and can generate high-pressure shock waves that can cause nucleation. These shock waves are strong when they are very close to the imploded bubble, but rapidly weaken as they propagate away from the implosion. See <i>sonocrystallization</i> .	26
<i>crystal</i>	solid material, whose atoms or molecules are arranged in a highly ordered microscopic structure, forming a periodic lattice structure. While snowflakes are singular ice crystals, ice itself usually is made of microscopic crystals fused into a single solid and is therefore a polycrystal.	22
<i>crystallizer</i>	device that releases the supercooled state of a liquid by promoting nucleation and crystal growth in a controlled manner.	17, 24, 29
<i>Gibbs free energy</i>	the thermodynamic potential that can be used to calculate the maximum amount of work that may be performed by a thermodynamically closed system at constant temperature and pressure.	22
<i>growth rate dispersion</i>	a phenomenon that same-sized crystals grown under identical conditions may show different crystal growth rates, leading to a non-uniform crystal distribution size.	24
<i>ice fraction</i>	<i>also:</i> ice packing factor. The ice fraction is the mass of water in the storage tank that is frozen in relation to the initial liquid water mass.	39
<i>ice packing factor</i>	see <i>ice fraction</i>	27

Notation	Description	Page List
<i>ice slurry</i>	pumpable mixture of small ice crystals or particles and a carrier fluid. Usually, the carrier fluid is either water or a mixture of water and a freezing point depressant, e.g. sodium chloride, ethanol, ethylene glycol and propylene glycol.	22
<i>ice-on-coil</i>	the most common heat exchanger method used in ice storages based on using evenly distributed embedded tubes on the outer surface of which ice forms.	15
<i>labile</i>	a labile system is in an unstable state and likely to undergo change. Supercooled water in the labile region is highly prone to spontaneous nucleation.	26
<i>melt</i>	A melt describes materials or solutions of materials that are usually solid at room temperature. This solution can be purified using the temperature-dependent crystallization temperature of its components in a process called melt crystallization.	27
<i>metastable</i>	a metastable system is a dynamic system in an intermediate energetic state other than its state of least energy. The system will spontaneously leave the metastable state to eventually return to the least energetic state.	22
<i>mixer</i>	device that increases the mass- and heat transfer rate within a fluid by increasing turbulence.	29, 32, 36
<i>nucleation</i>	initial formation of nuclei, when no ice crystals are present beforehand. This can happen homogeneously within the liquid itself or heterogeneously along the walls of foreign particles and objects.	22
<i>nuclei</i>	unstable, solid conglomerate of liquid particles, which may grow depending on thermal conditions. Stable nuclei that have grown larger than the critical radius are called crystals.	22
<i>secondary nucleation</i>	heterogeneous nucleation at the surface of an already existing seed crystal, with different crystal orientation.	22
<i>seeding</i>	introduction of ice crystals into a supercooled fluid to initiate crystal growth and subsequent attrition.	25
<i>solar-ice</i>	a solar and heat pump system that uses ice vessels as an intermediate storage device to store solar heat and delivers it to the heat pump evaporator when solar energy can't fully cover the evaporator's thermal needs.	15

Notation	Description	Page List
<i>sonocrystallization</i>	induction of nucleation and subsequent crystallization by means of ultrasonic bombardment in supercooled liquid.	26
<i>supercooler</i>	heat exchanger in which the liquid is supercooled.	16, 18, 20, 21, 24, 25, 27, 28
<i>supercooling</i>	cooling a liquid below its freezing temperature without it actually freezing.	22, 25
<i>supercooling degree</i>	temperature difference between the melting temperature and the actual fluid temperature.	19, 20, 22, 25
<i>supercooling release</i>	partial freezing of a supercooled liquid. A complete release will result in a bulk water temperature at the melting point and a solid fraction corresponding to the initial <i>supercooling degree</i> and the heat capacity of the material.	24
<i>supersaturation</i>	state of a solution when the concentration of a solute exceeds its solubility at equilibrium. A supersaturated solution is in a metastable state; it may be brought to equilibrium by forcing the excess of solute to separate from the solution.	22
<i>upstream propagation</i>	travelling of ice against the water flow, usually along walls where the flow velocity is zero.	24, 25

Abstract

Ice slurry generation technology with the supercooling method consists of cooling water below its melting point in a supercooling heat exchanger, called supercooler, therefore retaining this water in a thermodynamically metastable liquid state. Downstream from the supercooler, the supercooled water flows through a flow-based crystallizer where the supercooling potential is released by forming a water/ice flow mixture. In this process, the latent energy released by crystallization equals the sensible supercooling potential defining the percentage of the water that is converted into ice particles when forming the ice slurry flow. This latent energy is released in order to restore the thermodynamic equilibrium corresponding in equal internal energy to the metastable state from which it is formed. The greater the extent of supercooling achieved, the greater the quantity of liquid water that is converted into solid ice.

At the SPF Institute for Solar Technology we have been working with solar-ice systems for more than a decade. The solar-ice concept is a solar thermally assisted heat pump system that includes an ice storage component capable of bridging periods during which solar input is insufficient by itself to supply thermal energy to the heat pump's evaporator. The ice storage acts as a low-temperature seasonal storage to shift solar heat from summer to winter, while also being partially charged/discharged on a daily basis in winter to cover shorter periods with insufficient solar irradiation, e.g. nights or cloudy weeks. The ability to continuously charge and discharge, the use of water as both the heat transfer and heat storage medium, and water's large latent heat of fusion, collectively contribute to a leveled cost of storage outperforming most conventional, thermal energy storage technologies.

To further make the system more competitive by reducing installation cost, we proposed some years ago a novel approach using an ice slurry storage with the supercooling method. This concept was developed and demonstrated in the laboratory using the system evaluated within the H2020 project TRI-HP ([Gurruchaga et al., 2023b](#)). Simulation results have quantified the techno-economic performance of solar-ice slurry systems in many locations around Europe ([Gurruchaga et al., 2023a](#)). Besides the use in the residential heating sector, ice slurry systems have an untapped potential for shifting peak cooling loads. With the increasing demand of cooling and the need to stabilize the electrical grid with the increasing share of intermittent renewables, ice storage systems are positioned to become more relevant in the near future. Thus, developing a cost-effective solution to store cooling energy, serving both heating and cooling sectors, is very important. Due to its availability, negligible environmental impact, low unit cost of raw material, inherent safety, high latent heat of fusion and the infinite number of cycles of melting and solidification, water constitutes a very favorable phase change material having large potential to support the energy transition in a cost-effective manner.

Regarding supercooling ice slurry technology, there are three main challenges that remain to be addressed. The first one is to reliably supercool water in a heat exchanger (supercooler) and maintain stable supercooling in flow channels downstream, the second one is to crystallize water in what we have called a "flow-based crystallizer" without causing a blockage in the flow network (i.e., generating a fluidized suspension of ice-water), and the third one is to store the ice slurry into a storage vessel in a way that a high packing factor can be achieved while avoiding ice particles to be pumped back to the supercooler where they would cause crystallization within the supercooler.

Our approach to solve these challenges was to address them each separately when possible. Thus, we endeavored first to address the reliable supercooling phenomena, isolating this challenge from the remaining two. This approach was shown successful in a previous project and allowed us to study in detail the influence of icephobic coatings. The current project, Slurry-Store, was initiated in following to the previous work on the evaluation of these functional coatings. Thus, the challenge of supercooling water in stable form was solved before Slurry-Store began. In this regard, the current project had to face two remaining challenges: i) how to crystallize water properly and reliably and ii) how to store slurries efficiently in a storage vessel. While the main goal of the project was originally to study only the ice slurry vessel itself, without a proper crystallizer one cannot study how to introduce slurry flows in different forms. Thus, the project had to be restructured to tackle both challenges.

Within the Slurry-Store project, multiple crystallization methods and storage designs have been evaluated

and compared to each other. The resulting ice slurry production system uses pure, de-ionized water that is supercooled to as low as -2°C and converted to ice slurry using a flow-based crystallizer with ultrasonic transducers with a crystallizer efficiency around 77 %. The guiding principle behind the flow-based crystallizer was to generate ice slurries capable of being pumped for long distances while also being able to flow through 90° parts, mixing valves and other hydraulic elements without clogging the system.

To trigger nucleation in the crystallizer we have tested both Peltier and ultrasound technologies and selected the later. Our experiences in this project regarding the flow-base crystallizer have revealed three main challenges: i) to trigger efficiently the formation of ice nuclei; ii) to ensure that all supercooling energy is released, i.e. that all potential energy is converted into ice particles to avoid unwanted freezing elsewhere; and iii) to avoid upstream ice propagation. Each of these challenges was targeted individually with a specific solution, but all three needed to function correctly at the same time to successfully assess any single one of them. If one of the three elements fails, the system freezes and clogs quickly, adding considerable complexity to experimental evaluations.

Upstream ice propagation was solved using a film of warm water introduced just prior to the ultrasonic emitter. The effect of this thermal break, however, was the reduction of crystallization efficiency by 10 % to 13 % and that its effectiveness as an ice barrier was dependent on both the temperature and mass flow rate of the warm water flow. Since the inlet water to the thermal break was supplied from the inlet of the supercooler that was preheated above 0°C , it was not possible to analyze systematically and independently the effects of inlet temperature and mass flow rate. Thus, our approach was adapted to identify a consistently reliable working condition, deferring the optimization of parameters to a future project.

As soon as one crystal is formed within a supercooled flow, the difficulty in stabilizing the system for continuous operation increases considerably since crystallization propagates quickly throughout the supercooled fluid in both space and time. Our approach to ensure that no supercooled water was leaving the crystallizer and that the ice slurry would be in a pumpable form was to use a jet mixer. In spite of confirming the efficacy for this mechanism to stabilize the crystallization process so as to permit continuous operation and supporting the conditions to produce a pumpable ice slurry, it came with significant losses on the thermal power obtained through crystallization. The crystallization efficiency was reduced approximately to 13 % to 77 % due to the mixing of water superheated around 0.3°C , therefore reducing the mixed flow's overall supercooling degree. The first generation of jet mixers required mass flow rates two times greater than that of the main flow with crystallization losses up to 72 %. For the second generation of jet mixers, these losses were reduced to 13 % by implementing a design that could be operated with mass flow rate of 1:1 ratio compared to the main, supercooled flow.

The third challenge, regarding the efficient storage of slurry, was how to inject the ice slurries into the storage vessel to achieve a high ice packing factor. Several designs concepts for the introduction of ice slurries into the storage vessel were analyzed. All of these were based on introducing the slurries from the bottom of the storage in order to use a net on top to keep the ice fully submerged. In this way, we were able to measure experimentally the mass of ice by changes in the observed water level. Our idea was to introduce also the ice slurries from the top, but due to lack of time, it was not possible to do so. Moreover, introducing ice slurries from the top would defeat the measurement of ice mass with the aforementioned technique.

Several inlet port designs were also evaluated experimentally. Some of these designs were demonstrated to be working continuously for many hours (up to 40 h), but the overall ice packing factor of the whole storage was around 12 %, which is far from the objective of 50 %. Despite our original idea was to put the focus of the project uniquely on this part, the need to have a proper ice crystallizer consumed a large part of the budget and therefore the experiments for the ice slurry storage analysis itself were neither as extensively undertaken nor as detailed as initially proposed. In this respect, a follow-up project will be needed to conduct a detailed study of the ice slurry storage vessel to achieve ice packing factors approaching 50 % once a reliable, scalable crystallizer becomes demonstrated.

While studying the behavior of the ice slurry tank, several ice blockage events occurred that allowed us to study the patterns that could be used to indicate the kind of freezing event triggered from operational sensor logs alone. This is very important in order to study the different elements of the system, such as the inlet

ports into the storage vessel. Since these experiments were quite lengthy, most freezing events occurred when no one was present in the laboratory to record observations. Thus, clear indicators of what was the cause of the blockage will be important in order to study the influence of different elements of the system and to tune an appropriate control system response.

Finally, we developed a zero-dimensional, numerical ice slurry storage model that was validated using the experimental data. Numerical results have shown that the model was able to capture the global behavior of icing and forced melting accurately when the heat transfer coefficient was calibrated correctly (i.e., model tuning). The model has been implemented in pytrnsys-TRNSYS and successfully used in hundreds of simulations in other works ([Gurruchaga et al., 2023a](#)). However, the model idealizes the effective contact area between ice and liquid water that will be improved in near future. This will also allow us to calculate the heat transfer coefficient between solid and liquid water in a physical way.

Zusammenfassung

Résumé

La technologie visant la production des suspensions fluidiques d'eau glacée a comme but de refroidir de l'eau à une température inférieure à son point de fusion, effectuant une sursaturation du fluide par moyen d'un échangeur de chaleur dénommé « supercooler ». La sursaturation s'agit d'un état thermodynamique dit métastable. À la suite du « supercooler », le courant d'eau sursaturée devient dirigé vers un appareil produisant les conditions nécessaires pour la cristallisation de l'eau en écoulement, dénommé « flow-based crystallizer ». C'est dans cet appareil « flow-base crystallizer » que l'énergie potentielle de sursaturation est convertie en changement de phase partielle de la cristallisation d'eau en proportion du déficit énergétique nécessaire pour restituer l'équilibre thermodynamique. Suffit que ce processus se passe dans un état d'écoulement soutenu, le produit qui s'en issu s'agit d'une suspension fluidique d'eau glacée. Le plus fort le refroidissement de la sursaturation, la plus grande la proportion de la cristallisation de l'eau.

Depuis plus de dix ans, notre équipe appartenant à l'institut des technologies solaires SPF ait complété des développements techniques au sujet des systèmes d'énergie solaire avec stockage thermique en forme d'eau glacée, dits « solar-ice ». Il s'agit de systèmes de chauffage/refroidissement des bâtiments auxquels l'évaporateur de la pompe à chaleur à source d'eau est habituellement approvisionné d'énergie thermique solaire et, autrefois lorsque l'énergie solaire est absente/insuffisante, de tirer de la capacité d'énergie latente de l'eau à son point de fusion. La masse d'eau agit également comme stockage saisonnier surchauffé à basse température auquel est approvisionné l'énergie solaire de surplus en été ainsi qu'accommoder simultanément une capacité de charge et décharge lors des périodes plus courtes en hiver auxquels l'énergie solaire est pauvre (e.g., soirs et périodes nuageuses). La capacité de pouvoir à la fois se décharger et se charger d'énergie thermique de manière ininterrompue, utiliser l'eau comme médium d'échange de chaleur et de stockage thermique, ainsi que de posséder une énergie latente de cristallisation supérieure aux autres matériaux de changement de phase donnent ensemble aux systèmes « solar-ice » un coût nivelé préférable aux systèmes de stockage thermique autrement conçus.

Afin d'avantage réduire les coût des matériaux et d'installation nécessaires pour les systèmes « solar-ice », le SPF ait proposé, il y a plusieurs années, de les adapter au processus de sursaturation/suspension fluidique d'eau glacée. Ce concept fut réalisé et évalué en laboratoire lors du projet H2020 TRI-HP ([Gurruchaga et al., 2023b](#)) ainsi qu'évalué en tant que son potentiel techno-économique par simulation selon diverses localités en Europe ([Gurruchaga et al., 2023a](#)). En plus que leur application pour le chauffage des bâtiments résidentiels, il reste toujours à réaliser le potentiel des systèmes stockage d'énergie thermique à base de suspension fluidique d'eau glacée concernant leur capacité au déplacement temporel du refroidissement des bâtiments lors des périodes de haute demande d'électricité. Motivé par la croissance sans cesse du refroidissement des bâtiments ainsi que le défi d'équilibrer le système d'électricité avec toujours de plus grandes proportions d'énergies de sources renouvelables, les systèmes stockages d'énergie thermique à base d'eau glacée deviendront de plus en plus importants à l'avenir de la gestion des systèmes d'énergie. Donc, il est déjà évident que la mise à point des systèmes stockage d'énergie thermique de façon économique sera nécessaire en ce qui concerne l'avenir du développement durable du chauffage et refroidissement des bâtiments. Naturellement, l'eau glacée se présente uniquement préférable parmi les matériaux changement de phase pour réaliser l'avenir de la transition des systèmes d'énergie, de façon économique, selon sa disponibilité et coût faible, impacts environnementaux et risques à la santé négligeables, énergie latente de fusion élevée, ainsi que l'absence de dégradation cyclique lui donnant un potentiel infini de cycles charges/décharges.

En ce qui concerne la technologie de sursaturation/suspension fluidique de l'eau glacée, il se trouve principalement 3 défis qu'il faut surmonter. Le premier parmi eux s'agit de produire avec confiance un courant d'eau sursaturé par moins d'un échangeur de chaleur, dit « supercooler », et de le maintenir dans cet état à la sortie du supercooler. Le second s'agit de cristalliser l'eau sursaturée de façon contrôlée dans un appareil dénommé « flow-based crystallizer » auquel il faut surtout éviter l'évolution des blocages au débit d'eau dans le système hydraulique (i.e., produire avec confiance une suspension fluidique d'eau glacée). Le troisième s'agit de développer un réservoir pour la masse d'eau qui suffit d'entreposer une suspension d'eau glacée à fraction

cristallisée élevée sans que l'eau glacée devienne aspirée en direction du « supercooler » où elles causeront une panne du système.

Notre stratégie était celui d'adresser chacun des défis individuellement autant qu'il était possible. Alors, nous avons eu succès à surmonter le premier défi individuellement des deux autres, ayant évalué le rendement de plusieurs traitements anti-glaçage pour les échangeurs de chaleur dit « supercooler ». Concernant le projet actuel, Slurry-Store, nous l'avons poursuivi à la suite des succès au premier défi, envisageant d'adresser ensemble les deux prochains défis : i) comment cristalliser avec confiance les courants d'eau sursaturée de façon contrôlée (i.e., en suspension fluide); ii) comment entreposer les suspensions d'eau glacée dans un vaisseau évitant toutefois l'aspiration des particules d'eau glacée en direction du « supercooler ». Malgré le désir d'avoir adressé seulement le dernier défi concernant le réservoir d'eau glacée en suspension, il n'y aurait pas été possible de le réaliser sans poursuivre aussi le développement du « flow-based crystallizer » afin de pouvoir fournir au réservoir les suspensions d'eau glacée. Conséquemment, le projet actuel envisageait d'adresser ces deux défis simultanément.

Dans le contexte du projet Slurry-Store, plusieurs méthodes pour lancer la cristallisation du courant d'eau sursaturée de façon contrôlée et de nombreux modèles du réservoir d'eau glacée en suspension eux ont été évalués les uns contre les autres. Il a eu comme résultat de produire l'eau cristallisée de source pure (dé-ionisée), sursaturée jusqu'à -2°C et cristallisée de moyen des émetteurs ultrasonique, ayant l'effet ensemble de cristalliser avec une efficacité d'environ 77 %. Le principe par lequel nous avons poursuivi le développement du « flow-based crystallizer » était celui d'assurer que la suspension fluide d'eau glacée qu'il y eut produite aurait les caractéristiques suffisantes pour pouvoir s'acheminer d'assez longues distances ainsi que parmi les nombreux éléments hydrauliques qu'y si trouvent sans y causer un blocage qui aurait comme résultat de mettre le système en panne.

Afin de pouvoir déclencher la nucléation contrôlée à l'intérieure du « flow-based crystallizer », nous avons évalué le rendement des technologies utilisant les éléments de refroidissement Peltier ainsi que les émetteurs ultrasoniques, desquels le dernier fut sélectionné. Trois défis se sont faits évidents au cours des expériences : i) pouvoir déclencher effectivement le processus de nucléation ; ii) assurer que la totalité du potentiel de la sursaturation du courant d'eau se transforme en eau cristallisée, causant le retour à l'équilibre thermodynamique ; iii) éviter que la cristallisation d'eau sursaturée ne se procède en direction reculons. Malgré avoir adressé chacun de ces défis de façons individuelles, leurs évaluations nécessitaient de tout faire au même temps afin de pouvoir espérer de compléter les expériences sans interruptions causées par le blocage de glace.

Nous avons réussi d'éviter la cristallisation de reculons par moyen d'introduire une couche d'eau tiède dans le courant d'eau sursaturée à une position juste avant l'émetteur ultrasonique. Cependant, l'effet de cette sorte de « thermal break » a eu comme résultat de réduire le rendement de la cristallisation par 10 % to 13 % selon son caractère de réduire la sursaturation en proportion de son énergie thermique surplus qui se mélange avec le courant d'eau sursaturée. La réduction du rendement de cristallisation ainsi que son efficacité à garder contre la cristallisation de reculons dépendent à la fois de la température et du débit de l'eau tiède introduite. Puisque nous avons fourni cette eau tiède du « thermal break » du courant d'eau principal dirigé à l'entrée du « supercooler » qui était faiblement surchauffé juste au-delà de 0°C afin d'assurer que l'eau qui lui était fourni ne pouvait agir comme source de cristallisation spontanée, ni la température ni le débit ne pouvait être contrôlé de façons suffisantes à l'analyse systématique de leurs effets indépendants l'un de l'autre. Alors, en ce qui concernait ce projet-ci, il suffit d'identifier au moins une condition de cette eau tiède qui réussit avec confiance de pouvoir opérer le système sans interruptions. Conséquemment, les activités d'optimisations se devaient être reporté à plus tard.

Aussitôt que le premier cristal soit formé dans le courant sursaturé, il devient très difficile d'obtenir un état d'opération stable puisque la cristallisation a la tendance de se propager facilement et rapidement dans toutes directions, spécifiquement en reculons qui risque causer les plus grandes difficultés. Notre stratégie pour assurer qu'il n'y restait aucune eau sursaturée quittant le « flow-based crystallizer » et que la suspension demeurait toujours fluide était d'employer des jets pour bien mélanger le courant glacé. Malgré avoir réussi démontrer l'efficacité de cette stratégie pour chacune de ces exigences, il y avait comme conséquence de diminuer le rendement et puissance thermique de la cristallisation. Le rendement se trouvait dans la gamme de 13 % to 77 % selon la dilution du courant sursaturé avec les jets d'eau tiède (surchauffée environ 0.3°C), ayant l'effet

de diminuer le potentiel de sursaturation. Le premier prototype du « flow-based crystallizer » employant des jets d'eau tiède pour assurer l'opération stable et ininterrompue devait être alimenté d'un courant d'eau tiède du double le débit du courant sursaturé. Nous avons réussi de réduire cette proportion des débits au second prototype au taux de 1:1, ayant aussi diminué la perte du rendement de la cristallisation au montant de 13 % au lieu de 72 % qu'il y était pour le premier prototype.

Concernant le troisième défit, nous ayons visé de réaliser une proportion de glacement dans le réservoir d'autant que 50 % par masse. Plusieurs conceptions eues été analysées pour effectuer l'introduction au réservoir du courant d'eau glacée en suspensions issue du « flow-based crystallizer ». Toutes ces concepts représentaient des stratégies auxquelles la suspension était introduite au fond du réservoir afin de pouvoir capter la flotte d'eau cristallisée et de le garder submergée par moyen d'un écran. Ceci nous permettait de mesurer la tenu d'eau cristallisée dans le réservoir avec confiance selon le déplacement du volume d'eau liquide. Nous ayons eu aussi le désir d'effectuer l'introduction du courant suspension d'eau glacée du haut du réservoir, cependant le temps nous manquait et il y aurait fallu développer une stratégie alternative pour mesurer la tenu d'eau cristallisée dans le réservoir.

Nombreuses conceptions des orifices pour l'introduction du courant d'eau glacée en suspension au réservoir étaient évaluées lors du projet. Il y avait certain d'entre eux qui on réussit de démontrer une capacité pour l'opération de longue durée (j 40 h), cependant, la proportion de glace demeurait faible, environ 12 % de masse au lieu de l'objectif de 50 %. Malgré qu'il fût notre désir de concentrer nos attentions uniquement au développement du réservoir, il était toutefois nécessaire de développer un « flow-based crystallizer » fiable afin d'évaluer le réservoir dans les conditions représentatives. Par conséquent, ces développements additionnels ont consommé une grande partie du budget ainsi que le temps requis pour effectuer le projet. Dont que les activités du projet concernant le développement du réservoir ont dû être raccourci, il va falloir compléter ces activités parmi le contexte d'un projet suivant afin de pouvoir réaliser l'objectif de glacement à 50 % dans le réservoir.

Lorsque nous avons évalué le rendement du réservoir d'eau glacée, il y ait eu plusieurs occasions de blocages de glacement qui se sont produits desquels nous avons pu découvrir les causes apparentes afin de pouvoir les identifier selon seulement les données des capteurs du système. Ces observations furent importantes lors des évaluations du réservoir car les expériences devaient continuer pendant les soirs qu'il n'y avait personne présent pour effectuer des observations. Ces apprentissages nous assisteront sûrement à la détermination de cause des blocages selon les divers dispositifs qu'il y aura dans les différentes conceptions du système et pour adapter un système de contrôle électronique.

Dernièrement, nous avons réussi développer un modèle numérique de zéro dimension représentant le système « ice slurry » entier, ce que nous avons validé contre les données expérimentales. Les résultats obtenus du modèle numérique ont démontré les comportements du glacement et de fonte actuelle de façon globale, suffit que le modèle fût premièrement calibré au coefficients des échanges de chaleurs du système observé au laboratoire. Ce modèle fut mis en application avec le logiciel de modélisation pztrnsys-TRNSYS que nous avons utilisé pour effectuer des centaines de simulations dans autres ouvrages ([Gurruchaga et al., 2023a](#)). Cependant, nous remarquons ici que le modèle numérique se fiait sur une conception idéale de la superficie de contact entre l'eau cristallisée et l'eau liquide que nous voudrions améliorer lors d'un projet au futur. Lorsque nous réalisons cette amélioration du modèle numérique, nous serions capables de déduire correctement le coefficient d'échange de chaleur entre l'eau cristallisée et liquide qui y ait lieu des expériences au laboratoire.

1 Motivation

Ice storages have a very large variety of applications, from building cooling using both decentralized or centralized concepts with district cooling networks (Kozawa et al. (2005a)) to industrial applications such as breweries and dairies as well as commercial refrigeration for food conservation (Kauffeld et al., 2010)). Furthermore, this method has an unexploited potential for heating applications in the residential sector with the so-called *solar-ice* systems (Carbonell et al., 2021). The currently used *ice-on-coil* ice generation method uses an anti-freeze heat transfer fluid that flows through embedded tubes in a water vessel forming ice on the outer surface of the tubes. This approach has the advantage of relative simplicity without moving parts. However, the heat exchangers represent a significant cost that scales with capacity, making the levelized cost of storage less competitive. In addition, the low thermal conductivity of ice forms a self-insulating layer, which limits the amount of ice that can be formed per heat exchanger unit surface area. One method to avoid having ice growing on a heat exchanger surface is to use ice slurries.

Commercial ice slurry systems use mechanically scraped-surface heat exchangers, where ice is formed on a cold surface and is then removed continuously by a rotating mechanical arm that scrapes ice from a cylindrical barrel. The scraping mechanism creates ice shards that fall to the bottom of the barrel from where are transported away. The scraper design, having a mechanical component, requires high operation and maintenance cost, and has limited potential for scale up due to the mechanical constraints of the rotating-scraping arm. Thus, what is needed is a passive concept for ice slurry production that does not rely on moving and that has high efficiency such as the supercooling method combined with a flow-based crystallizer. Improving energy efficiency, reliability, and reducing installation as well as operating costs of ice slurry systems will allow Swiss and in general European industry to exploit the potential of ice slurry technology.

Solar-ice systems have been a topic for research at SPF for more than 10 years. For further information about *solar-ice* systems in general the reader is referred to other SFOE funded projects carried out at our institute such as Carbonell et al. (2017a, 2021), Philippen et al. (2015). Today, it is clear that the Swiss energy system will include a lot of heat pumps to supply residential buildings with heating and cooling (Marcucci et al., 2021). However, which heat sources these heat pumps will use will depend on many factors such as ground water regulations, social acceptance including the noise of fans for Air Source Heat Pumps (ASHP) as well as aesthetics, waste water availability, etc. Thus, in order to cover many local and regional needs, several heat sources for heat pumps need to be considered. In this context, solar-ice is usually seen as a substitute for Ground Source Heat Pumps (GSHP) since it can achieve the same efficiency with the additional benefit of not needing to drill boreholes. When compared to GSHP, *solar-ice* offers an often missed benefit. It does not need further regeneration in the long term since it regenerates on a yearly bases. Thus, one can see *solar-ice* systems as equivalent to GSHP systems with full ground regeneration. Despite of these benefits, state-of-the-art solar-ice systems have usually a higher investment cost compared to GSHP if the same performance is desired. Therefore, research is still needed to bring robust solar-ice systems to the market with comparable cost and higher efficiency with respect to ground-source heat pump solutions.

In the current project we are targeting a particular case of solar-ice system called solar-ice slurry system whose simplified concept scheme is shown in Figure 1. The key devices of the proposed system are the supercooler, i.e. the evaporator of the heat pump, the flow-based ice crystallizer and the ice slurry storage. The main benefits of an ice slurry system with supercooling method compared to the ice-on-coil are the cost reduction of the ice storage due to the elimination of heat exchangers in the storage vessel and the system efficiency increase due to the avoidance of ice growing on the heat transfer surface. The proposed concept can reduce the complete system installation cost significantly.

The use of ice slurries with the supercooling method for *solar-ice* was firstly proposed in the feasibility study carried out in Carbonell et al. (2017b). This work showed that *solar-ice* systems based on the ice slurry approach have a high potential for cost reduction. At the same time, these systems can have a high energetic efficiency, especially for ice storage volumes of at least 1 m^3 per MWh of yearly heating demand, which corresponds well to ice storage volumes used today for multi-family buildings (MFH). It would even allow to use existing rooms of the building efficiently since any shape and room size could theoretically store ice slurries if one finds a way to evenly distribute the ice particles among the volume. In Gurruchaga et al. (2023b) the

Figure 1: General scheme of a solar ice-slurry system.

investments costs of the solar-ice slurry systems were estimated to be between 8 % to 11 % lower than the reference ice-on-coil system in Bilbao and between 14 % to 17 % lower in Zurich. The heat generation costs in ct/kWh were between 7 % to 12 % lower for the slurry version. Moreover, the system is conceived such that the used heat exchanger (*supercooler*) is always free of ice and thus has a higher efficiency compared to the ice-on-coil method for large ice fractions.

The development of the ice slurry technology using the supercooling method has three main challenges: i) supercooling water below 0 °C in stable form; ii) crystallizing water in a controlled manner to avoid upstream ice propagation and high-efficiency supercooling release; and iii) pumping and storing slurries without clogging with proper separation between solid to liquid water in a storage vessel.

The first challenge has been a topic of study in several works discussed in section 1.3. In order to carry on the current project we had previously conducted a long research to develop supercoolers using icephobic coatings to ensure a stable and large enough supercooling is possible. Our first breakthrough was achieved showing experimentally how brazed heat exchangers could be used to cool down water down to -3°C to -4°C when icephobic coatings were used (Carbonell et al., 2022). To our knowledge, these large degree of supercooling were not achieved before in industrially relevant heat exchangers. The best performing supercoolers were installed in a propane and a CO_2 heat pump with a thermal nominal capacity of about 10 kW. The energetic performance of the propane heat pump including supercooling conditions were presented in Gerber et al. (2022). This propane slurry heat pump was coupled with a complete system that was tested using the method of the concise cycle test presented in Haberl et al. (2022). Results of the test from both propane and CO_2 heat pumps have been published in Gurruchaga et al. (2023b). Moreover, the complete system was analyzed by means of co-simulations to assess the benefits of using model predictive controls in Péan et al. (2022). The cost-economic analysis around Europe was presented in Gurruchaga et al. (2023a). Therefore, despite work might still be necessary to assess long term durability of coatings and their applications in different type of heat exchangers, the first challenge of supercooling in stable form is relatively solved. Within this context, the current Slurry-Store project makes use of the supercoolers developed previously and is targeting the two other challenges, i.e. the flow-based crystallizer and the slurry storage design.

The overall goal of the Slurry-Store project was to experimentally investigate ice storages able to store and melt

slurries without using a stirring device. The specific objectives of the project were: i) to design, construct and test an ice slurry storage tank capable of achieving 50 % ice mass fraction (ice packing factor), ii) to develop, construct and test an *ice crystallizer* for stable continuous ice slurry production of 6 hours, iii) to design, construct and test concepts for loading (icing) and unloading (melting) and iv) to develop a mathematical model for the ice slurry storage and validated it with experimental data.

During the project we have reach all the goals mentioned above. However, not all measurable targets were achieved as anticipated. Namely, the ice packing factor measured of 12 % has been significantly lower than the targeted 50 %. The main cause has been the lack of time due to the large resources devoted to develop a working crystallizer, which was way more challenging than anticipated. On the other hand, the target of 6 h of continuous ice production without freezing was achieved by operating the system for more than one full day in a stable form.

1.1 Working principle

A scheme of the supercooling concept with a flow-based crystallizer to produce ice slurries is shown in Fig. 2. The concept is as follows: liquid water at the melting temperature is pumped to the heat exchanger where it undergoes supercooling. Right after the supercooling, the flow is disturbed and forced to nucleate in a controlled manner and location in what is called a crystallizer. After the crystallizer, all supercooling sensible heat is converted into latent energy, and thus solid crystals are formed. Since the ice slurry is not supercooled anymore, it can-not freeze anywhere else, thus avoiding clogging and unwanted nucleation in other parts of the system. For the concept to work, the solid particles need to be "separated" in the storage vessel from the liquid part, since the liquid phase will be pumped into the supercooler again. The density difference between solid and liquid allows this separation, but the storage needs some internal design to ensure no solid particles are pumped back into the supercooler. Usually, a small preheating (0.3 K above melting temperature) is used before the supercooler to ensure any small particle is melted. Typically, the maximum solid mass fraction, i.e. the ice packing factor, can be around 50 % in the ice slurry system (Tanino and Kozawa, 2001).

Figure 2: A working principle of an ice slurry concept with supercooling.

A scheme of a current crystallizer is shown in Fig.3. The first ice particles are generated due to the cavitation induced by the ultrasound device. These particles are attached to the walls where the velocity is zero. Despite the flow pushing the growing ice from the walls away, some micro-particles are kept on the walls making the ice slurry production possible even if the ultrasonic transducer is not operating. The ice particles on the walls act as seeding for the continuous crystallization process. The shape of the ice pushed away in this design is like a ring since ice grows on the walls. This shape makes the pumping very difficult, thus it needs to be broken. After the first ice particles are formed, they grow on the way downstream. To accelerate particle growth and to break the ice shape we introduce a water jet at 0 °C, which makes the system stable at a cost of increasing exergetic losses reducing the overall crystallization efficiency.

Figure 3: Scheme of the created crystallizing unit, consisting of barrier, ultrasonic emitter and mixer.

1.2 Ice slurry production methods

Within the project we have focussed on the supercooling concept. However, the production of ice slurries can be achieved in multiple ways (Ernst and Kauffeld, 2016, Kauffeld et al., 2005, Mouneer et al., 2010, Zhang and Ma, 2012):

- **Scraper design** includes a moving scraper that periodically or continuously remove the ice crystals from a heat exchanger wall. It is one of the simplest and most common methods, but involves moving parts, and requires motor power. Its scalability is limited due to the force acting on the scraper arm and the required motor power.
- **Orbital rod generators** Orbital rods work similar to the scraper design. A moving whip rod is used to de-ice the surface, which is commonly the inner wall of a tubular heat exchanger. Unlike the scraper design, it does not touch the exchanger walls and usually moves much faster compared to the scrapers.
- **Fluidized bed generators** use moving beads whirled inside the fluid flow. These beads randomly hit the heat exchanger wall removing the ice crystals that grow on the wall surface.
- **Supercooling method** separates the location of cooling and nucleation. Thus, ice does not grow on the heat exchanger surface and no moving parts are needed.
- **Direct contact heat exchangers** benefits from a large heat transfer between the icing fluid and the immiscible refrigerant which are in direct contact. As the icing fluid transfers heat to the refrigerant, the latter evaporates and can then be then removed from the freezing fluid.
- **Vacuum ice slurry generation** works using states close to the triple point of water. Cooled water is sprayed into a deep vacuum, such that part of the water evaporates. The latent heat of vaporization is removed from the remaining liquid water, which then freezes.

In our study, the method of supercooling will be used, since it does not require additional energy for e.g. motors, it does not utilize moving parts and its technology readiness level is believed to suit best the foreseen application as a heat source for heat pumps.

1.3 Ice slurry production by supercooling

To be able to create a high degree of supercooling, the formation of ice needs to be prevented as long as possible. While the desired high degree of supercooling is the main driver for crystallization, the likeliness of formation of ice can be lowered by influencing the free energy of nucleation.

The supercooling method suffers from unstable operation, and this has limited further market deployment, specially in Europe where not a single system has been installed nowadays. One of the challenges is to avoid or reduce the formation of ice on the surface of the *supercooler* heat exchanger. A second challenge is to provoke ice formation when desired by promoting ice nucleation and controlling the ice concentration for proper distribution in the ice storage. Undesirable ice growth in the coldest part of the heat exchangers may cause blockages, and although the process is self-sealing, the refrigerant cycle operation is stopped and an extra energy and supply system for melting the ice formed is necessary.

Ice nucleation is stochastic, i.e. ice will not nucleate at the same temperature and time during a cooling process on apparently identical surfaces; however, the probability of nucleation increases exponentially with the degree of water supercooling. Also, the probability of freezing increases with the time that supercooled water is in contact with a surface. Therefore, a safe margin of the degree of supercooling and duration of

ice slurry production needs to be considered in order to achieve a high probability of nucleation suppression. The availability of nucleation sites and the probability of nucleation can be reduced several methods described below.

Methods to reduce the probability that ice nucleates on, grows on, and adheres to a surface – and thus to increase the *supercooling degree* and long-term performance of the system – include reducing the roughness of the surface, which reduces the area and the likelihood of nucleation. [Faucheux et al. \(2006\)](#) analyzed the influence of aluminum roughness on the supercooling degree under static conditions concluding that it increases when surface roughness decreases. Roughness between $0.63\ \mu\text{m}$ to $13.33\ \mu\text{m}$ were analyzed leading to 8.5 K and 4.2 K supercooling degrees correspondingly. Thus, lowering the surface roughness was found to increase the supercooling degree significantly. These investigations showed very high supercooling degrees, but are not entirely applicable to continuous processes since they were obtained using static conditions. [Ernst and Kauffeld \(2016\)](#) analyzed the influence of aluminum roughness on the supercooling degree under steady flow conditions of 265 kg/h and roughness of $0.4\ \mu\text{m}$ to $2.1\ \mu\text{m}$. They reported a maximum supercooling degree with a continuous cooling process of 3 K. After that temperature, the pipe was blocked by ice formation.

A common approach to avoid or delay ice nucleation is to use hydrophobically coated surfaces. Lowering the contact area between water and the heat transfer surface increases the surface free energy, reducing the probability of nucleation at the surface. [Saito and Okawa \(1994\)](#) investigated the effect of the heat transfer surface characteristics on the freezing of supercooled pure water. It was observed that the supercooling degree was highly dependent on the characteristics of the surface.

[Jung et al. \(2011\)](#) report that surfaces with very low roughness in the range of the critical nucleation radius and high wettability display longer freezing times compared to superhydrophobic surfaces with a very low wettability, although these surfaces are also reported to reduce ice formation. The property of a high water contact angle of superhydrophobic surfaces seems to be competing with the desired low roughness. They conclude that superhydrophobicity does not necessarily need to be equal to *icephobicity* and suggest finding an optimum between wettability and low roughness. These findings were confirmed by [Hejazi et al. \(2013\)](#), who suggested to widen the expression of icephobicity to include the property of low adhesion strength of ice to the surface to facilitate the removal of ice. [Janjua et al. \(2017\)](#) observed that the adhesion strength of ice to a surface is lowered with high receding *contact angle* and low contact angle hysteresis. Recently, [Carbonell et al. \(2022\)](#) studied the effect of several smooth icephobic coatings on brazed heat exchangers. All coatings showed better supercooling degrees and the best coating achieved in average about 40 % higher supercooling degree compared to an uncoated heat exchangers.

The effects of fluid flow regime on supercooling degrees is still unclear ([Kauffeld and Gund, 2019](#)), but in [Carbonell et al. \(2022\)](#) it was shown that the supercooling degree decreased significantly when the mass flow rate was doubled. [Ronceray and Harrowell \(2017\)](#) state that slowing down the kinetics of the liquid reduces crystallization speed, since this lowers heat and mass transfer rates of the liquid close to a growing nucleus. In [Luo et al. \(2019, 2020\)](#), the effect of shear flow on ice formation is simulated. It is concluded that the shear rate influences different mechanisms. An increase of the shear stress increases the free energy barrier for the nucleation, lowering the likelihood of a nucleus to become a stable crystal. At the same time, the existence of a shear stress increases the diffusion and the formation of nuclei. At low shear rates, the increased growth of an ice nucleus dominates. As the shear rate increases, the exponential relation to the increased energy barrier for nucleation dominates and reduces the nucleation rate. However, these findings are strongly dependent on the supercooling degree, which dominates the aforementioned effects. Similar behaviors were reported for ice growth rates. Again two effects compete: at low shear rates, shear mainly breaks the hydrogen bond network of water, allowing water molecules to reorganize and bond with the existing ice. At higher shear rates, shear predominately disrupts the water-ice hydrogen bonds, reducing the growth of ice. At temperatures close to the freezing point, these effects are dominated by thermal effects.

1.4 State of the art on supercooling

There is a significant gap between Japan and the rest of the world on the know-how and state-of-the-art of ice slurry technologies, especially in supercooling-based methods. Already in 2001, the number of ice slurry

systems in operation was far larger in Japan than in any other country of the world (Kauffeld and Gund, 2019). It is likely that the large difference between night/day electricity tariff and the cost reduction that the supercooling method has the potential to bring pushed the research community together with a large number of industrial players to work on that topic. There are at least three companies in Japan that commercialize ice slurry systems using the supercooling method: Takasago Thermal Engineering, Mayekawa and Shinryo Corporation. These companies use large heat exchangers to overcompensate the instability of the supercooled fluid and the partly blocked heat exchangers. At a certain point, even these systems need to be shut down and thawed, which is obviously inefficient. Some literature state that a *supercooling degree* of 2 K is achieved. However, the real metrics of freezing times and technical difficulties are not communicated. It is worth noticing that these companies do not operate at all in Europe so it is not possible to use or test any of their systems in Europe.

There are several publications from the research group of the Japanese company Takasago Thermal Engineering where they explained the concept of supercooling. Researchers from this company presented an ice slurry generator with a capacity of 13 kW with 2 K of supercooling (Kozawa et al., 2005b, Tanino and Kozawa, 2001). Unfortunately, no details on the heat exchanger type or surface treatments used in the *supercooler* were given. Moreover, nothing was mentioned about the stability, reliability and icing frequency of the system.

The state-of-the-art in Europe, and in general everywhere else except Japan, is far below in the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) chain. Castaing-Lasvignottes et al. (2006) and Bédécarrats et al. (2010) investigated numerically and experimentally a *supercooler* heat exchanger, where stable operation was achieved with 1.2 K degree of supercooling, leading to slow ice production and only 1.3 kW cooling power. In their experiments, supercooling of 2 K was found to be unstable. The heat power with this low supercooling degree of around 1.3 kW was not enough to completely evaporate the refrigerant and a second evaporator was used for this purpose. The same heat exchanger was used in the following experiments by Bédécarrats et al. (2010). In these new experiments, a maximum supercooling degree was found to be 2 K, but blocking was very frequent. For supercooling degrees below 1.2 K there was no blocking, but ice production was very slow. Between 1.3 K and 1.9 K there were regular blockages (less than 2 per hour). It was found that the achievable supercooling degree increased by lowering the flow rate, but at a cost of producing lower quantity of ice. It was found that for the same supercooling degree, higher flow rates lead to a higher number of blockages which was explained with the assumption that turbulence promotes crystallization. These experiments showed that achieving stable operation with a decent *supercooling degree* is challenging.

During analyses of the roughness of a coaxial copper tube with supercooled flows, supercooling data was provided by Ernst and Kauffeld (2016). Tap water was supercooled in a coaxial tube heat exchanger with an inner diameter of 8 mm, a length of 5 m, a total area of 0.24 m² with a cooling capacity of around 1.2 kW. Using a mass flow rate of 265 kg/h the maximum degree of supercooling was 3 K. Roughness was varied between 0.4 μm and 2.1 μm and the degree of supercooling was 2.3 K and 3 K, respectively, using a water velocity of 0.36 m/s. The supercooling degree was higher than the ones reported by Bédécarrats et al. (2010) and Castaing-Lasvignottes et al. (2006). While the frequency of ice blockages as a function of the maximum supercooling degree that was achieved was not stated in the paper, the authors reported by personal communication that the supercooling degree was stable over several hours. However, these results were obtained using a polished long tube with gentle bends and only 1 kW of cooling capacity. This kind of heat exchanger is not suitable for any practical application.

In Wang et al. (2012), the authors coated a coaxial tube heat exchanger (12 mm internal diameter) with a polymer that contained a fluoroc binder and an organic solvent. They observed an increase in the maximum supercooling degree from 0.9 K to 1.7 K at a velocity of 2 m/s thanks to the fluorocarbon coating. However, even with the coated surface, this highest supercooling degree only lasted 9 minutes. Increasing the velocity to 2.5 m/s lead to frequent blockage by the ice growth. It was also observed that the maximum supercooling state lasted 6 minutes for the uncoated surface and 9 minutes for the coated one when tap water was used. The maximum supercooling degree was obtained with velocities of 2 m/s. Values below 1.5 m/s were not able to produce any slurry and above 2.5 m/s the heat exchanger was frequently blocked by the growth of ice. To address the problem of not achieving continuous ice production due to ice blockage, the same authors in Wang et al. (2016) proposed a double uncoated *supercooler* concept, such that once an ice blockage exists

in one *supercooler* a second one would operate. In this paper, a corrugated flat plate was used with a degree of supercooling in the range of 0.5 K to 1 K with low fluid velocities of 0.1 m/s to 0.45 m/s.

Recently, [Carbonell et al. \(2022\)](#) showed experimental results of several industrially relevant icephobic coated heat exchangers using two mass flow rates with fluid velocities up to 0.08 m/s approximately. The results of the best coating achieved averaged supercooling degrees close to 4 K, but the supercoolers were operated at half its nominal mass flow rate. When these heat exchangers were implemented in a real heat pump and operated with nominal mass flow rates and velocities up to 0.16 m/s ([Gerber et al., 2022](#)), the supercooling degree used was also around 2 K like most other works proposed to avoid unwanted nucleation. In these two later works the phenomena of water supercooling was separated from the ice nucleation and ice slurry management by completely avoiding ice particle formation. This was an important factor on the testing method used that allowed to isolate the supercooling phenomena, i.e. making it independent on the uncertainties of improper ice slurry management.

The combination of water supercooling with ice crystallization in a closed cycle is more challenging than working only on the supercooling phenomena. Producing ice slurries on the system is likely to lead to a decrease of the supercooling in a stable form. The main reason is that crystallizing ice in a controlled manner is not that simple, mainly due to the combination of ice crystals in supercooling flow that will naturally tend to freeze making difficult the control of the process. Moreover, one also needs to make sure ice particles are not pumped to the supercooler again, otherwise freezing will occur in the heat exchanger. Thus, as soon as ice particles are present in the system the supercooling degree achieved depends on many factors and it is crucially important to separate these effects when studying them.

2 Ice slurry theory

Ice slurry is a mixture of small ice crystals or particles and a carrier fluid. Ice crystals are in the size of 0.1 to 1 mm; when they are above 1 mm they are usually referred to as ice particles (Kauffeld et al., 2010). Usually, the carrier fluid is either water or a mixture of water and a freezing point depressant, e.g. sodium chloride, ethanol, ethylene glycol and propylene glycol.

2.1 Nucleation kinetics

The classical *nucleation* theory (CNT) (Fisher et al., 1949) explains that the formation of ice, i.e. the phase change from liquid to solid form, occurs via a *metastable* state that can be reached via *supersaturation*. This supersaturation can be achieved either with pressure, concentration and/or temperature variations (*supercooling*) (Kauffeld et al., 2005). In this metastable state, small clusters of water molecules, *nuclei*, are formed due to statistical thermal spatial fluctuations. The following nucleus growth is a result of a series of equilibrium mechanisms that correspond to the local free energy of nucleation, which in turn is related to the free activation energy for the short-range diffusion at the phase transition interface (Fisher et al., 1949). If thermal conditions favour the growth of the nucleus, its size may increase beyond the critical radius. Further growth above the critical radius releases energy and spontaneous growth occurs. If the fluctuations do not favour growth, the smaller nuclei below the critical radius may decay and eventually dissolve. The creation of nuclei from a purely metastable state is called *homogeneous nucleation* and its formation rate depends exponentially on the *supercooling degree*. The change in *Gibbs free energy* ΔG is the difference between the volume free energy ΔG_V and the surface free energy ΔG_S . It depends on the number of molecules n , the change in chemical potential per molecule in water and ice $\Delta\mu$, the surface area A and the surface tension between ice and water γ_{iw} . The expression reads as:

$$\Delta G = -\Delta G_V + \Delta G_S = n\Delta\mu \cdot A\gamma_{iw} \quad (1)$$

In practice, most nucleation processes are formed due to heterogeneous nucleation, which describes nucleation at foreign surfaces. As the free energy of nucleation is the sum of the counteracting parts of the volume free energy and the surface free energy, these counteracting parts behave differently in the presence of foreign surfaces. The resulting heterogeneous work of nucleation is lower than the homogeneous work of nucleation by a factor that depends on the interface and the geometry of the surface. Heterogeneous nucleation requires lower degrees of supersaturation compared to homogeneous nucleation. Equation 1 is then extended by the additional term ΔG_{St} , which denotes the strain induced by the interface such as surface lattice misfit, surface heterogeneity, defects, roughness and type of bonding. Thus, ΔG can be expressed as:

$$\Delta G = -\Delta G_V + \Delta G_S + \Delta G_{St} \quad (2)$$

If heterogeneous nucleation occurs at the surface of an already existing seed crystal, it is called *secondary nucleation* (Myerson, 2002). After a nucleus has grown larger than the critical radius and has become stable, it is called a *crystal*. The process of crystal growth follows different mechanisms:

- **Crystal growth:** A crystal which is in contact with supercooled water will grow by incorporating water molecules at its surface. This crystal growth mechanism controls the particle size distribution of the slurry mixture. It can be modelled using a kinetic equation that includes the molecular diffusion through the boundary layer as well as the incorporation of the molecules into the crystal surface:

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = k_G \cdot A \cdot \Delta C \quad (3)$$

where A and m are the surface area and the mass of the crystal, t is the time, k_G is the overall mass transfer coefficient and ΔC the change of concentration at the boundary layer. The mass transfer coefficient is calculated using the mass transfer coefficients of diffusion and incorporation (k_i):

$$\frac{1}{k_G} = \frac{\delta}{D} + \frac{1}{k_i} \quad (4)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient and δ the boundary layer thickness.

- **Attrition:** refers to the process of crystal breaking into smaller pieces when subjected to stress. This can be due to collision with other solids, e.g. other crystals or walls or due to a high fluid shear, e.g. during mixing.
- **Spheroidization:** is the process in which the dendritic ice is shaped more like a sphere while flowing in the tubes due to the more thermodynamically favorable surface of a sphere. The mechanisms are Ostwald ripening and attrition.
- **Agglomeration:** is the process in which two crystals collide and adhere to each other forming a single crystal. This process increases in a highly supersaturated suspension. Once agglomerated, the crystals can further coalesce and sinter, forming a more stable crystal.
- **Ostwald ripening:** is the process in which large crystals tend to grow due to their smaller surface-to-volume ratio compared to smaller crystals nearby that tend to dissolve.

Nucleation can be achieved by dynamic stimulation, a form of heterogeneous nucleation. In this case, the energy to create an embryo or nuclei is provided by pressure pulses, vibration or friction e.g. using ultrasonic waves. When using ultrasound, the nucleation rate is driven by the cavitation produced. However, this mechanism is only relevant at the starting phase when the ultrasound device is active. Afterwards, the ice crystals formed adhere to the walls and are the main source of nuclei formation. This is known as secondary nucleation, which is a complex phenomena not well understood (Myerson, 2002). A general theory to predict nucleation rates does not exist. However, several approximations based on power law models have been used to fit experimental data. Considering the effects of fluid flow, the nucleation rate B can be expressed as:

$$B = k_N \Delta C^n Re^m \quad (5)$$

where B is the nucleation rate expressed as $no./m^3 \cdot s$, ΔC is the concentration change and Re the Reynolds number, k_n , n and m are coefficients to be found by experimental data. However, the equations above are used for crystallization on solutions where the driving force for crystallization is the change of concentration of the solute to induce supersaturation. In our case we only have one component and the driving force is the supercooling degree. The crystallization process of ice in supercooled water is dominated by heat transfer and not by mass transfer as in solutions. In an ice slurry, the solid particles are surrounded by water and in an isothermal process close to the melting temperature.

2.2 Crystal growth

After the nuclei achieved a certain size considered as nucleation, the crystal will grow. Both nucleation and crystal growth determine the final particle size distribution of the slurry system. In order to define the crystal growth rate one needs to assume a shape for it. Typically, a spherical shape is assumed in which the characteristic length is the diameter of the particle. Although this can be useful to understand the process it is far from reality. We do observe many different shapes that depend on the shape of the crystallizer and the operating conditions. For example, in a tube, we do observe an annular ice shapes that are attached to the walls and pushed away by the fluid flow.

A generic equation to describe crystal growth is to formulate the change of crystal mass per unit time:

$$R_G = \frac{1}{A} \frac{dm}{dt} = 3 \frac{\alpha}{\beta} \rho \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (6)$$

where R_G is the increase of mass per unit surface area and unit time $kg/(m^2s)$, A is the surface area of the crystal, α and β are the volume and area shape factors respectively, ρ the crystal density and L the characteristic length.

The kinetics of crystal growth can be described using the diffusion layer model (Myerson, 2002). However, this theory is based on crystallization due to changes in concentration in a solution. Thus, we need to adapt

this model to our case in which the driving force is not supersaturation produced by changing concentration, but rather due to supercooling. Thus, the crystal growth is dominated by heat transfer:

$$\frac{dm_c}{dt} = D \cdot A \cdot \left(\frac{dT}{dL}\right) \quad (7)$$

When a crystal is growing from a supercooled solution, this creates a temperature difference between the liquid-solid interface and the liquid supercooled water. This generates a heat flux leaving the crystal along the boundary layer thickness δ . Thus, Eq. 7 can be written as:

$$\frac{dm_c}{dt} = \frac{D}{\delta} \cdot A \cdot (T_{melt} - T_{sc}) = K_d \cdot A \cdot (T_{melt} - T_{sc}) \quad (8)$$

where T_{sc} is the supercooling temperature of the bulk water and T_{melt} is the melting temperature of 0 °C. The growth rate constant K_d is temperature dependent and usually expressed using the Arrhenius equation:

$$K_d = A \cdot \exp^{-E_G/RT} \quad (9)$$

where A is a constant, E_G the activation energy and T the absolute temperature in Kelvin. In the classical Arrhenius law, R is the universal constant of gases.

The theories mentioned above assume that crystal growth is independent of crystal size, which is not always true. Some theories stipulate that large crystals will grow faster due to the higher surface area and thus have a higher probability of having surface dislocations. However, there is another phenomenon called *growth rate dispersion* which also affects size-dependent growth. There are two main theories that attempt to explain growth rate dispersion. One theory stipulates that crystals have a distribution of growth rates, but that each individual crystal size grows at constant rate. The other theory states that all crystals grow at the same average rate, the growth of each individual crystal has large fluctuations. Thus, the latter is based on a kind-of stochastic behaviour of ice growth in which same size particles under the same boundary conditions might grow at a different rate momentarily, but on average over time they will grow at the same rate. To explain this phenomenon the model of *Burton-Cabrera-Frank* (BCF) has been used. The BCF is a continuous crystal growth model in which the dislocations of existing crystals are the source of further growth. Collisions of crystals can lead to an increase in dislocations and thus further growth

The equations described above can be useful for understanding ice kinetics in static applications. However, they are far too simplified to handle the complexity of a flow-based crystallizer with supercooling conditions. Basically, we are lacking the understanding of the influence and coupling of fluid flow mechanics with crystal growth rates and thus the applicability of the theory described above is very limited for our application. Thus, for the current project, our approach was based purely on experimental proof-of-concepts without numerical design tools that could support our designs.

2.3 Ice crystallizer - supercooling release methods

During the project, it was found that the ice *crystallizer* has to fulfill three different purposes.

- **First**, trigger ice nucleation from ice-free supercooled water, which is hereafter called the nucleation method.
- **Second**, avoid ice propagation in a counter-current direction towards the *supercooler*. This part is sometimes called *upstream propagation* prevention in literature; the term *ice barrier* however is also common.
- **Third**, ensure a complete release of the supercooling degree to prevent freezing downstream of the crystallizer and thus to enable transportation of the ice slurry towards the storage tank. This function is called *supercooling release*.

The above functions of the crystallizer are subject to development in the current project and scientific papers on these topics are scarce. Most information in this field can be found in Japanese patent publications summarized in section 2.3.2. More information about the experimental work done during this project and further description of the entire ice crystallizer unit can be found in chapter 3.

2.3.1 State of the art of prevention of upstream propagation

Inaba et al. (1994) describe the behavior of ice growing from supercooled water flows within a pipe. They mention ice growing in an annular shape on the inside of a pipe wall that can either be ejected by the the main water flow or, if *supercooling* is large enough, lead to blockage of the pipe. If the main water flow is strong enough and peeling occurs due to the flow, microscopic crystals remain on the original bonding surface, and new ice nuclei grow from the same spot again. Via this mechanism, ice tends to crawl upstream along the pipe walls, until it cannot be flushed away by the flow any more, resulting in blockage. This process is called *upstream propagation*.

This challenge is tackled in different ways in literature: early developments use an open and free-falling stream on the ice storage (Mito et al., 2001a, Tanino and Kozawa, 2001). Thus, in this concept, the crystallizer is within the ice storage vessel using the collision of the supercooled fluid with a different surface as crystallization method (method (i) in section 2.3.2). Another approach shown in Fig. 4a use constant ultrasonic bombardment to remove ice from the pipe and crystallizer walls (Nagato, 2001, Tanino et al., 2000), which is simultaneously also the crystallization method mentioned in method (ii) in section 2.3.2. Mito et al. (2001b) and Mito (2002) propose a thin laminar water flow layer at temperatures above 0 °C introduced into the inside of the pipe to prevent ice propagation (Fig. 4d). The warm film above 0 °C has a flow rate of about 2 % to 3 % of the supercooled water, which has a velocity of approximately 1 m/s. Another concept shown in Fig. 4c uses recirculated water streams injected into the tube to heat the internal wall surface to temperatures above 0 °C (Yaoji, 2015). Tadamasu et al. (2006) propose to use a shell of warm water flowing parallel to the supercooled main flow to release supercooling without ice propagation (Fig. 4b). Water sources above 0 °C with a mass flow rate of at least 3 % of the supercooling flow were estimated to be necessary.

Figure 4: Four different designs of crystallizers with parts for upstream propagation prevention. a) Ultrasonic bombardment from Tanino et al. (2000) b) Warm water flow shell from Tadamasu et al. (2006) c) 0 °C recirculation from Yaoji (2015) d) Warm laminar water flow within pipe from Mito (2002)

2.3.2 State of the art of crystallization methods

Controlled release of the supercooled state of the water allows to adjust ice particle size, slurry properties and prevents ice from blocking pipes. Crystallizers should therefore be close to the *supercooler* and should allow the complete release of the *supercooling degree*. Except for crystallization through *seeding*, four approaches are reported (Wang et al., 2016, Zhang and Ma, 2012):

- (i) Collision of the supercooled fluid with a different surface. This may be a solid, a free liquid surface in a tank or a collision of multiple supercooled flows (Bédécarrats et al., 2010, Yoshiyuki et al., 1993, Yuichi et al., 1998). Crystal agglomeration near the impact place needs to be considered. Wang et al. (2016) used a 400-mesh sieve filter with 37 μm apertures.
- (ii) Ultrasonic vibrations are reported to be an effective means of controlled release of the supercooled state. A fluid exposed to power ultrasound (20 kHz to 100 kHz) undergoes acoustic *cavitation*, i.e. the sudden formation and collapse of gas bubbles in liquids. This process is reported to cause nucleation of ice from supercooled water (Baillon et al., 2015). During this process, high temperatures (up to 5000 K) and pressures (up to 100 MPa) can be generated on micro-scale, as well as outward propagating shockwaves causing severe turbulence (Cheng et al., 2015). The so-called *sonocrystallization* typically results in smaller but larger number of crystals compared to crystallization without ultrasound. Sonocrystallization is mainly used in the food industry to influence the freezing pattern in standing water. There, the goal is to induce crystallization that does not harm the internal structure of the food products (Ma et al., 2021).
- (iii) A patent from Kazuhiko and Yuji (1991) described an ice making device from supercooling flows using a propeller and impeller to provoke cavitation. The energy used to convert the cavitation bubbles back to liquid are triggering nucleation, as in method (ii). However, the presence of cavitation at the impellers can damage the impeller itself due to the violent collapse of the bubbles.
- (iv) Locally increasing the supersaturation from the meta-stable to the *labile* region by e.g. a local reduction of temperature, increases the probability of nucleation. However, this threshold is, among others, strongly dependent on the supersaturation rate and set-up (Mullin, 2001). Therefore, this method can be used e.g. by utilization of small and local electrical cooling as done by Kurihara and Kawashima (2001) or by changing the properties of the pipe. Le Bail and Havet (2015) use different types of surface roughness over the length of their tubular heat exchanger to promote crystallization. They report continuous production of ice slurry using a water-ethanol mixture, but also state a big impact of the flow velocity on the crystal growth pattern. They achieved dendritic crystal growth, resulting in ice slurry plugs that were pushed out of the heat exchanger. Different materials within heat exchangers with varying heat transfer rates could also help nucleation.
- (v) The influence of electric and magnetic fields in nucleation was repeatedly researched. Although it was shown that both types of field influence the supercooling degree, the crystallization rate and the quality of crystallization, the mechanisms do not seem to be fully understood (Dalvi-Isfahan et al., 2017).

2.3.3 Supercooling releaser

The aim of a supercooling releaser on one hand is to guarantee small ice crystals, which reduces the likeliness of conglomeration and, as a consequence, blockage (Ahmadkermaj et al., 2021). This can be achieved either by breaking larger particles or by promoting the formation of a large number of nuclei.

On the other hand, a supercooling releaser should efficiently remove any residual degree of supercooling while occupying a small space, to prevent supercooled water to freeze somewhere else. From an energetic point of view, the sensible heat from the supercooling state is transformed into solid particles and thus equal to the latent heat of fusion. Thus, the mass of ice generated M_{ice} can be calculated from the mass of supercooled water M_{water} , the supercooling degree ΔT_{sc} , specific heat of water c_p and latent heat of fusion h_f as follows:

$$M_{ice} = M_{water} \cdot \frac{c_p}{h_f} \cdot \Delta T_{sc} = 0.0126 \cdot M_{water} \cdot \Delta T_{sc} \quad (10)$$

Thus, for a pumped ice slurry, the ratio of solid to liquid mass of water, the so-called ice packing factor, can be calculated as:

$$IPF_{flow} = 0.0126 \cdot \Delta T_{sc} \quad [kg_{ice}/kg_{water}] \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{m}_{ice} = IPF_{flow} \dot{m}_{water} \quad [kg_{ice}/s] \quad (12)$$

For a typical supercooling degree of 2 K one can calculate from Eq. 11 that only 2.5 % of the total flow will be converted into solid ice. The simplest but least efficient method to release the supercooling sensible heat in terms of time and space is to just wait until the ice crystals have grown themselves until a complete crystallization is achieved. In that case, the ice growth rates of [Kallungal and Barduhn \(1977\)](#) and [Fernandez and Barduhn \(1967\)](#) would apply. In a continuously operated system, this would lead to a large apparatus to grant the required residence time, and depends on the available space, mass flow and degree of supercooling.

To reduce the space requirements of the crystallizer different methods have been reported. One method to increase the crystallization speed is to increase heat and mass transfer. An efficient way to do so is to use forced convection, e.g. by mechanically mixing or by inducing turbulent flows ([Cussler, 2009](#)). [Yaoji \(2015\)](#) structure their crystallizer such that highly turbulent flows occur at their crystallizer inlet. [Tadamasu et al. \(2006\)](#) use a similar approach, and additionally force ice crystals to pass through the newly arriving supercooled water, increasing contact time between ice crystals and supercooled water (see Figure 4b). [Tanino et al. \(2000\)](#) permanently bombard the supercooled water with multiple arrays of ultrasonic transducers, largely increasing the amount of nuclei and increasing cavitation on a microscopic level. They found a distinct connection between the ultrasonic bombardment time and the supercooling degree at the crystallizer outlet; with a reported 4.1 s as minimum bombardment time for full supercooling release. They chose a centrifuge water flow inducing geometry for their crystallizer, as did [Koji et al. \(1992\)](#). The reason for such a design is the gravimetric separation of ice and water, with ice being dragged towards the center of the fluid flow. Contact of ice with the walls can be reduced this way, lowering the risk of accumulation and blockage. Literature regarding design guidelines of supercooling releasers is scarce and mostly only described in patents, where dimensions do not need to be given. Classical literature regarding design of crystallizers usually describes crystallization processes from solutions or *melt*, and rarely include continuous crystallization from freezing ([Myerson, 2002](#)).

2.4 State of the art on storage design

A properly designed storage tank optimizes the stored amount of energy. This value is measured using the *Ice packing factor* IPF which is the percentage of ice in the tank by weight. It can be measured by centrifugal separator, by calorimeter and by the volume change method ([Inaba et al., 1994](#), [Kang et al., 2001](#)). A centrifuge simply separates water from ice at a constant temperature, such that both can be weighted afterwards. The calorimetric method measures the energy required to heat the entire tank or a sample to a desired temperature. The volume change method forces ice to be completely submerged and measures the change in liquid level during freezing and melting. The precision of the different methods have been subject to research and debate, since small measurement deviance can lead to large errors in IPF.

[Kauffeld et al. \(2005\)](#) summarizes various tank designs, whereas un-agitated designs with storage inlets from the top achieve the highest IPF of up to 50%. Melting inlets as spray from top as well as mixed tanks can be found as well. [Tanino and Kozawa \(2001\)](#) and later also [Kozawa et al. \(2005a\)](#) propose a model for the relation between ice inlet mass flow, time and achievable IPF for an ice inlet from the top of the tank. They state a trade-off between loading time, IPF and the uniformity of the ice spread in the tank.

Proper tank design can also reduce the amount of ice pumped to the *supercooler*. One of these concepts is described in the patent from [Yuichi et al. \(1998\)](#), where multiple tanks are added in series. Another concept is described by [Kobayashi et al. \(2003\)](#), where the distance to the exit is prolonged using the buoyancy force of ice.

2.5 Conclusion on literature review

Multiple approaches for the supercooling release were found during the literature review. Early methods as e.g. collision or supersaturation release were reported already around twenty years ago and did not seem to be a technological barrier in the examined papers. These methods however seem to be either unreliable or require large devices. The newer sonocrystallization method is reported to allow controlled nucleation and is

widespread in more recent patents and papers. It has the benefit of being non-invasive, reliable and it produces a large number of small nuclei, which in return helps to remove supersaturation quickly.

According to the conducted review, a key to a successful crystallizer is to prevent ice crystals to propagate upstream and to prevent blocking of the pipes between the *supercooler* and the crystallizer. Interesting ideas have been presented, but most technical solutions seem to be concealed in papers and patents. Unlike heated walls or introduced hot water flows, an ideal solution would not require any additional energy.

The second crucial part of a successful crystallizer seems to be the ability to render the ice slurry pumpable. This topic is scarce in literature since only a few groups use pure water in their systems, and this topic does not seem to be an issue for water-glycol mixtures. A solution needs to be found that does require no or only little energy and reliably produces a pumpable, fully developed ice slurry.

The Slurry-Store project does not focus on the development of supercooling heat exchangers. However, functional supercoolers are necessary in order to produce ice slurries for the project. Developments at SPF show that we can supercool water with a capacity of at least 10 kW using a mass flow of 2000 kg/h. The literature research shows that this supercooling power has not been achieved in Europe before using industrially relevant heat exchangers.

3 Experimental Work

During the three years of the project, a set-up for testing supercooling and ice generation was planned, built and altered several times. Various improvements were found to be necessary and were applied consequentially. The different parts and alterations are described in chapter 3.1. The current ice slurry generator concept is able to operate using tap water as a carrier fluid with a 2 K supercooling degree at a mass flow of 400 kg/h, releasing its supercooling degree in the ice crystallizer with arbitrary piping parts mounted between the crystallizer and the tank. The set-up can be operated at a mass flow rate of 1000 kg/h at the same supercooling degree when entering the tank directly from the crystallizer without obstacles in between. This supercooling degree has the potential to lead to an ice slurry flow with a IPF_{flow} of 2.5 % that is pumped into the tank. We have operated this systems for over forty hours with the 1000 l tank. However, there are several limitations and new challenges that were found during the project that had to be tackled.

- **Inducing crystallization (ice crystallizer):** Crystallization can be induced using several methods, as described in the theoretical chapter 2. The currently preferred method is the use of ultrasonic wave bombardment, which works reliably for the necessary operating conditions. An ultrasonic transducer converts an electrical wave signal into an ultrasonic sound wave using the piezoelectric effect. The sound wave provokes cavitation which in turns enhances crystallization due to the high local pressure change on the fluid flow. However, in our experimental set-up, it requires a supercooling degree above 1.75 K to successfully induce crystallization. It is certainly possible to trigger crystallization at lower supercooling degrees. However, our set-up had large wave transmission losses into the fluid. After the required bombardment time, ice is attached at the inner pipe walls and continues to grow along the walls. This device is described in section 3.1.1.
- **Prevention of upstream propagation (upstream ice barrier):** As soon as ice grows at the inner pipe walls, it starts propagating towards the coldest points, i.e. towards the supercooling heat exchanger. The water velocity at the pipe wall has the no-slip boundary condition, i.e. zero velocity. This means that ice at this location is not flushed away by the water flow until its volume grows into the main flow. Even then, ice is not fully removed, and ice nuclei are still present at the rough spots of the inner pipe wall leading to a continuous ice growth. During this process, ice grows towards the supercooler until the heat exchanger or other obstacles are reached anywhere else between the supercooler and the crystallizer, both resulting in clogging the system. Thus, a mechanism is needed to prevent upstream ice propagating along the pipe walls. A design to accomplish this task, called *ice barrier*, was proposed and tested successfully. The upstream ice barrier is described in section 3.1.2.
- **Ice pumping and distribution:** The currently used crystallization design described in section 3.1.3 has ice growing mainly at the pipe walls, resulting in a loosely connected, cylindrical ice shape. It is pushed away from the pipe by the water flow as soon as its resistance to the water is larger than its adhesion to the pipe wall. It is, however, strongly susceptible to blockage if there are obstacles on its path towards the tank. Experiments have shown that already edges of few tenths of a millimeter on the pipe walls can be enough to lead to blockage of the entire pipe. A device, called *supercooling releaser* or colloquially just *mixer*, had been designed, built and tested to deal with this challenge.
- **Tank design, separation of ice and water:** A certain cause of blockage is the presence of ice at the entrance of the supercooler. If ice nuclei are present at this location, blockage is almost inevitable. This leads to the challenge that the feed water flow to the supercooler needs to be completely ice free, even though it is connected to the ice slurry tank. Other approaches address this challenge by simply pre-heating the water flow entering the supercooler until all ice particles are melted. Preliminary experimental results showed that the required energy input and reliability is linked to the amount of ice that is present at the tank outlet. The design of the tank and the way how the ice slurry flow is introduced into the tank influence the amount of ice present at the tank outlet and can be used to optimize energy efficiency.

Figure 5: Piping & Instrumentation Diagram of the current set up.

Figure 6: Image of the current setup. The control cabinet is visible in the top left corner, the IBC storage tank on the right side and the crystallizing unit (horizontal pipe connected to the storage). The two chillers are not shown.

3.1 Experimental set-up for supercooling ice production

The target of the described installation is to continuously produce ice slurry with a 2 K supercooling degree. This will lead to a continuous ice slurry flow of roughly 2.5 % solid content respect to the main supercooled flow¹. The design of the installation is based on the setup of a previous project, in which the supercooling capability of an icephobically coated flat plate heat exchanger was tested. The setup is schematically shown in Fig. 5. It consists of three separate piping loops: i) a glycol-water mixture loop with 30 % glycol content (left side of *PHX1*) to cool down the water loop to the desired temperature, ii) a loop with softened water (right side of *PHX1*) and iii) a second glycol-water loop to pre-heat the supercooler inlet water flow (secondary loop of *PHX2*). The loops are connected via plate heat exchangers: the supercooler *PHX1* and the (pre)heater *PHX2*. The entire setup is insulated using 13 mm *Armaflex* insulation. It is controlled using the software *Labview*. PID controllers automatically adjust the power of both Lauda-thermostats and the pump rates. All PT-100 sensors are calibrated in-house using a 5-point calibration, resulting in an error of max. 0.15 °C. The glycol loop i) connected to the chiller is operated at 2750 kg/h and made from EPDM-hoses "trix rotstrahl". The water loop is made from transparent PVC pipes with $d_i = 27.2$ mm and can be operated from 350 l/h to 3500 l/h. The used volume flow range lies mainly in the transition regime between laminar and turbulent flows ($2300 < Re < 10000$). The calculated Reynolds number for the selected mass flow rates are listed in Tab. 2.

Table 2: Reynolds numbers of selected mass flows, with $\rho_{wat} = 999.87$ kg/m³, $d_i = 27.2$ mm, $v_{wat} = 0.001792$ Pas

Mass flow [kg/h]	Re
400	2901
1500	10884

$$Re = \rho_{wat} \cdot v \cdot d_i / \nu_{wat}$$

The cold glycol-water loop i) is controlled using the air-cooled process thermostat Lauda IN 1030 T (left device on Fig. 5). Its mass flow is achieved with its internal pump and measured by *FI-Gly*, an Endress+Hauser Promag 10H. The temperature is measured internally in the chiller as well as with the PT-100 temperature sensor *TI-2*, which is installed upstream (left part) of *PHX1*. The warm glycol-water loop iii) is controlled using a Lauda T4600 thermostatic bath, which stabilizes the water temperature at the inlet of *PHX1*, measured by the PT-100 *TI-5* via the plate heat exchanger *PHX2*. The main water flow is driven by a Grundfos pump and controlled using an Endress+Hauser Promass 300 flow sensor (shown as *FI-Wat* in Fig. 5). Temperatures are measured using several 4-wire PT-100 temperature sensors. Temperature sensors *TI-2*, *TI-5* and *TI-6* are used to control the temperatures before and after *PHX1* on hot and cold sides. The temperature sensors *TI-13* and *TI-14*, together with the volume flow sensors *FI-Bar* and *FI-Mix* are used to control the barrier and the mixer inlets respectively. The temperature sensors *TI-7* to *TI-12* are used to monitor the behaviour of the storage tank. *TI-7* is mounted directly at the tank outlet, while *TI-8* to *TI-12* are centered within the tank in 5 cm, 20 cm, 35 cm, 50 cm and 63 cm distance counting from the bottom of the tank. The temperature sensor *TSH* includes a mechanical safety switch to prevent overheating in case the heater would run without fluid flow. The temperature sensor *TI-15*, installed after the crystallizer mixer can be used to measure the successful removal of supercooling, but poses an obstacle to the transported ice. Complete release of supercooling must be ensured, otherwise freezing occurs at this sensor. The electric current delivered to the pump together with data from flow measurement is used to detect blocked pipes. Once ice is detected, a melting program is initiated. In this program, the temperature is increased by the chiller, reverting the cycle from cooling to heating in order to melt the ice formed in the system.

Before entering the supercooler, the water flow coming from the ice storage is heated up to 1.05 °C inside *PHX2* to ensure that no ice particles are pumped to the supercooler. Further reduction of this temperature can be subject to further development. After passing a static mixer that ensures the flow is well mixed, the mass flow rate is measured using a Coriolis mass flow meter. It then passes a filter with 5 μ m mesh size to remove possible solid particles before it reaches the supercooler. In the supercooler, the water is cooled down to temperatures between -1.75 °C to -2.5 °C, where icephobic coated surfaces inhibit the formation of

¹assuming no thermal gains are present in the crystallizer

Table 3: Equipment and instrumentation used in the experimental set-up

Description	Identifier	Make	Model
Chiller	EI-C	Lauda	IN 1030 T
Coriolis Mass Flow Meter	FI-W	E+H	Promass 300, DN15
Electric Heater	EI-H	Walser	RDL 70, 7 kW
Filter (Strainer)	-		5 μm mesh
Flow Meter	FI-Mix	Gams	173940
Flow Meter	FI-Bar	Gams	212460E
MID	FI-G	E+H	Promag H300
Peltier Module	-	DollaTek	TEC1-12712
Plate Heat Exchanger 1	PHX1	AlfaLaval	CBXP52
Plate Heat Exchanger 2	PHX2	Wegmann	WPL 7W1-GG-30-1-1/L
Pump	P-W	Grundfos	CME
Preheater	-	Lauda	T4600
Static Mixer	-	Kwerk	STRPE32
Temperature Indicator	TI-1 to TI-15	Transmetra	4-wire PT100 Cl. A

ice.

After the supercooler, the supercooling state is released in the ice crystallizer, which is a custom made device consisting of three parts. In the first part, a device to avoid ice propagation upstream, the so-called "ice barrier", is installed. A small flow (roughly 3 % of the main flow) with a temperature above 0 °C is taken from the main flow after being preheated by *PHX2*. It bypasses the supercooler (*PHX1*) and is then again inserted into the main flow through a slit in the pipe wall. This mechanism efficiently prevents ice from propagating towards the supercooler. Downstream of the barrier, an ultrasonic transducer is mounted on the outer wall of the pipe to trigger ice nucleation within the pipe. Ice particles start to grow at the rough pipe wall and are flushed away by the main flow, but some nuclei remain attached on the inner side of the pipe wall, becoming the seeds for further crystals. The third part of the ice crystallizer, the so-called *mixer* is a jet-type mixer and consists of a device that injects a large flow (roughly one to two times larger than the main water flow) of cold tank water through two tangential inlets to thoroughly mix the main flow. This breaks ice particles up in smaller ones and pushes it towards the center of the pipe due to differences in density, rendering it pumpable. All of these parts are crucial to improve pumpability and to prevent formation of ice in unwanted places, where it could clog the pipe.

3.1.1 Inducing crystallization

Using Peltier elements

Initial versions of the crystallization device used a Peltier module (make *DollaTek* TEC1-12712, 40x40 mm size, $Q_c = 107$ W) that was introduced into the flow: the Peltier element locally decreases the water temperature, which increases the likelihood of nucleation. In our experiments, the adhesion of ice to the Peltier was rather large and that the Peltier itself was acting as obstacle while flushing ice away. No stable operation condition could be found using this method for any of the tested flow conditions and pipe diameters ($\dot{m} = 500$ kg/h...4000 kg/h, $d_{in}=27.4$ mm...80 mm). This design is depicted in Fig. 7 a). As next option, the Peltier element was mounted to the outside of the pipe, assuming that cooling of the pipe wall would cool down the inside of the pipe wall enough to trigger nucleation. This trial did not lead to any success, even with

Figure 7: Different versions of the crystallization module. a) a peltier module was introduced into the middle of the flow to start nucleation. Ice release failed and blocked the flow after a short time. b) the peltier module (white plate) is on the outside of the pipe, connected with a 1 mm hole to the cold flow. Cooling of the outside of the peltier was required during operation, but the flow could operate unhindered. c) Ultrasonic transducer clamped to the pipe wall.

the reduction of pipe wall thickness from 2.4 mm to 0.5 mm. Then, the Peltier module was inserted into the pipe wall, such that it replaced pieces of the wall. There, once again, the high adhesion of ice to the Peltier module prevented flushing of ice and lead to blockage. It was found that attaching a Peltier module to the outside of the pipe wall but inside a 1 mm wide cutout from the wall lead to some success. This is depicted in Fig. 7 b). Ice formation could be triggered successfully if the supercooled water was below -1°C . However, sealing of the Peltier module to the pipe seemed to be troublesome and cooling the outside of the Peltier during operation might not be an easy task in a real system. Furthermore, for water flows above 1000 kg/h, the method could not be proved to work reliable.

Using ultrasonic bombardement

Due to the above reasons, the method of ultrasonic bombardment was installed: the ultrasonic wave produces a high local pressure change in the fluid (cavitation) leading to nucleation in the supercooled liquid. A 45 kHz, 50 W ultrasonic (US) transducer was clamped to the pipe wall using a custom made, stainless steel clamping plate, see Fig. 7 c). The chosen frequency of 45 kHz together with the speed of sound in water at 0°C of 1403 m/s leads to a wavelength of 31.18 mm. With a standing nodal point at half of this wavelength, at least one node will be within the pipe diameter: $\lambda/2 = 15.59 \text{ mm} < 27.2 \text{ mm} = d_i$. Assuming 100 waves necessary to supply enough energy to induce cavitation, 0.0022 s are needed. Within this time, water travels 0.43 mm, which is considered negligible ($\dot{m} = 400 \text{ kg/h}$, $d_i = 27.2 \text{ mm}$). Various reports state successful generation of ice using frequencies and powers close to the chosen one (Cheng et al., 2015, Hozumi et al., 2002, Ma et al., 2021, Zhang et al., 2001).

The transducer could also be screwed directly to the pipe, but the pipe wall is too thin to insert screws into it. Also, doubling up and increasing the pipe thickness hinders the effect of the ultrasonic bombardment. The transducer emits ultrasonic waves, leading to local evaporation of water. This evaporated water is not in thermal equilibrium with its surrounding, which is why the vapor bubbles immediately collapse violently, provoking cavitation. The high pressures that result from cavitation promote nucleation inside the bulk water. This method successfully started nucleation with supercooling degrees equal and above 1.25 K for the tested mass flow rates of 400 kg/h and 1000 kg/h. The resonance of the tube due to the US waves in combination with the implosions of cavitation helps to remove ice from the pipe wall during the US operation, preventing ice from attaching and growing at pipe walls locally. Thus, crystal growth is only observed away f waves

are active. The advantage of this method is its flexibility and reliability. The transducer can be attached to almost any shaped pipe or duct without altering the container in which ice nucleation is desired as the device stays outside of the flow. During the tests, it was found that the reliability and the bombardment time could be optimized using an ultrasonic transmission gel. It is also expected that pipes made from metal increase the reliability due to the increased transmission properties of this material compared to the current PVC pipes.

3.1.2 Prevention of upstream ice propagation

During the experiments, it was found that after initiation of crystallization ice mainly grows at the pipe walls and slowly grows upstream. As stated at the beginning of chapter 3 and in section 2.3.1, a device is needed to prevent ice from reaching the heat exchanger or any other parts in the pipe that could lead to blockage. Initial experiments used a trace heating cable (make *HTS Systems, DEV/pipeguard 25*, 2 m, 25 W/m) that just heats the outside of the pipe wall, leading to an elevated temperature at the inside of the pipe. The heat tracing concept can be seen in the Fig. 7 b) (red cable). This was found to be working for low degrees of supercooling and low flows ($< -1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $< 500\text{ kg/s}$), but failed with higher degrees of supercooling. Insulation and a stronger heating cable (40 W/m) did not improve this method noticeably. Furthermore, it consumes electricity, which could reduce the overall efficiency of the system.

Figure 8: a) and b) CAD drawings of two proposed ice barrier designs. Slightly warm water above 0°C is fed into the main stream from the top and through a narrow annulus gap in the pipe wall, preventing ice from growing upstream (from right to left). Main water flow direction is from left to right. c) and d) are pictures of the respective prototypes.

As an alternative to heat tracing, [Mito \(2002\)](#) proposed a device that is supposed to form a barrier to the ice, and efforts were made to replicate such a device. The idea of this device is to introduce a low-flow water stream that is slightly above 0°C , in which ice does not grow. This water flow is currently taken from the system after the installed filter ("Strainer" in Fig 5), thus by-passing the supercooler *PHX1*. With this concept, ice can not adhere to the pipe wall where this warm stream is injected, allowing the main flow to flush it away. Two different geometries shown in Fig. 8 were investigated. The designs depicted in Fig. 8 a) and c) were constructed and tested. It allows to operate at conditions above 3 K supercooling degrees with a mass flow rate of the main flow of 1000 kg/h. Stable conditions were found with barrier water temperatures of 2.2°C at a barrier mass flow 0.5 kg/min, which corresponds to 3 % of the main flow. The design shown in Fig. 8 b) and d) was tested and operated at conditions of up to 2.25 K supercooling degree and 1000 kg/h main water flow. However, the required barrier mass flow was more than 50 % higher compared to version a), which is why this design was not used any more. Another design was considered, where the wall of a piece of piping was heated with a second warm water flow. CFD simulations showed that using water coming from the

Figure 9: CFD simulation of a third barrier design, where a flow of warm water is used to heat the pipe walls of the supercooled water to prevent ice propagation. The supercooled water flow enters from left to right, the warm stream flows top down.

preheater at 0.5 °C (literature value of lowest possible preheater temperature) would still result in negative wall temperatures of the pipe, independent of the used warm water mass flow (see Fig. 9). Due to these results, a prototype of this design was not manufactured.

3.1.3 Ice pumping and distribution

Figure 10: First generation of mixers. Different designs of tested mixers: a) 32 mm straight through with screw connection between crystallizer and mixer. b) 32 mm straight through with clamped connections, 10 x 2 mm holes. c) 40 mm diameter straight through, glued. d) 80 mm mixer with reductions, mixing happens within the first expansion of the pipe.

In the first design of the ice slurry generator, ice was pumped into the tank using only a straight piece of piping after the crystallizer. To increase flexibility and modularity, various piping pieces were added between crystallizer and storage tank. It was observed that slight changes in the ice-leading piping (e.g. elbows,

reductions, fittings) and improperly built passages between pieces could lead to blockage. This study made clear that a close proximity between crystallizer and tank would be necessary if the supercooling degree would not be completely released, and even if this is the case, uneven surfaces inside of the pipes were to be avoided. This might not be always possible on a future system design and a solution was needed. The goal is to be able to pump the ice slurry flow through an arbitrary distance of piping with valves and other devices. To achieve this goal, all supercooling needs to be released as quickly as possible.

The operating principle of the proposed *mixers* device uses a water mixture from the ice slurry storage, which is fed into the main flow downstream of the US transducer. The required added mass flow depends on the mixer design, temperature, inlet velocity and on the properties of the main flow. For the first design generation, the mixer was functional with mass flow rates approximately twice the main mass flow rate. The inlet of this second flow is drilled tangentially, such that a vortex is created inside of the main pipe. The induced turbulence strongly mixes the main water flow breaking the large ice parts into small pumpable pieces. After this *mixer*, the supercooling degree is completely released featuring a water temperature of ± 0.1 °C after its use. Multiple mixer types have been built and tested. They are shown in Fig. 10.

The first design, shown in Fig. 10 a), had a 32 mm pipe and a screw connection between crystallizer and mixer. Twelve holes with 2 mm diameter were drilled into the main pipe, connecting the main pipe with the mixer flow as mixer inlet, acting as a jet-type mixer. The screw connection was the main location of ice accumulation and blockage. The main water flow for most of these tests was 400 kg/h and the mixer flow was around 780 kg/h, resulting in velocities of 0.18 m/s main flow and 5.7 m/s for the mixer flow at the inlet holes. The high velocity at this location enforces turbulence. Simultaneously, bigger ice crystals are broken up into smaller ones, increasing the surface area of the ice. Both effects strongly increase heat and mass transfer, which reduces the required residence time until the supercooling is released entirely. However, adding a fluid with temperatures above the melting point reduces the crystallization efficiency since not all of the supercooling potential can be converted into ice crystals.

The second design in Fig. 10 b) uses a clamp-on design which does not require the screw connection from Fig. 10 a). It gives access to the drilled holes, which can be altered to study the effect of amount and angle of the mixer inlet holes in future research. This mixer version has a low volume, resulting in a residence time (from barrier to mixer outlet) of roughly 8.2 s. The residence time is calculated as follows:

$$\tau_{mean} = \frac{V_1}{\dot{V}_{main} + \dot{V}_{barrier}} + \frac{V_2}{\dot{V}_{main} + \dot{V}_{barrier} + \dot{V}_{mixer}} \quad (13)$$

with τ_{mean} the average residence time in [s],

V_1 the volume between the barrier and the mixer inlet and

V_2 the volume between mixer inlet and mixer outlet.

Increasing the residence time by increasing the pipe diameter was the idea behind design Fig. 10 c). This pipe has a 40 mm diameter throughout the entire length of the pipe, resulting in a residence time of 15.1 s, and mixer inlet holes as built in design a). It is again glued due to a lack of available clamped standard pipe parts in the required sizes. A substantial improvement could not be measured using this mixer type. The reduction following the mixer was a frequent cause for ice accumulation and blockage.

The mixer shown in Fig. 10 d) increases the residence time to 18 s. It is the only tested design with an increase in pipe diameter (from 32 mm to 80 mm) after the US transducer. This increase in pipe diameter increases the mean residence time and renders the residence time more homogeneous among the various ice particles. The majority of the residence time in c) is in the pipe upstream of the mixer. In d), roughly half of the residence time lies within the agitated region after the mixer inlet increasing the mixer performance. It uses only two inlets with 10 mm diameter, resulting in an outlet flow velocity of 1.4 m/s. This velocity could still be optimized in future works. It was successfully tested with supercooling degrees and main water mass flows of up to -2 °C and 400 kg/h respectively. All experiments presented in section 3.2 were conducted using this mixer type.

Using the Fig. 10 (d) design, the ice slurry could be led through multiple consecutive elements such as elbows, reductions, PT-100 sensors and even a hose. However, further studies are required to improve the energy efficiency (reducing the required water flow) and increase the reliability at higher main flow velocities and higher ice fractions. For the transport of slurry without residual supercooling, it has been noticed that reductions and expansions as well as dead flow areas (e.g. hose connections) pose a greater risk for ice accumulation and blockage. These should be added to a system only with special care. Agitated flow., e.g. by induced turbulence and vertical mounting of these pieces seem to mitigate the risk.

3.1.4 Tank design: separation of ice and water

The stability of the ice generator is dependent on the ability to completely eliminate ice slurry particles pumped into the entrance of the supercooler. If any ice particle enters the supercooler, ice will grow rapidly and blockage of the supercooler will be inevitable. This means that the feed water to the supercooler needs to be completely ice free, even though it is connected to an ice filled storage tank. Most publications heat the inlet flow to the supercooler to 0.5°C to reduce the probability of pumping ice particles into the supercooler (Tanino and Kozawa, 2001). In the present setup, this temperature was not sufficient to prevent ice reaching the supercooler and blocking the flow at this point. Early tests using an electric heating rod had shown that a set point of 1.5°C needs to be used to prevent freezing reliably. The electric rod was assumed to heat the flow unevenly. This required more energy for heating and thus decreased efficiency. As a consequence, a plate heat exchanger with 0.9 m^2 heat exchanger area was added to the setup as a preheater instead of the electric rod heater. The higher heating area heats the water flow more evenly. Additionally, a static mixer was added to ensure even temperature distribution within the flow. Further, the previously used strainer with 0.5 mm mesh size was replaced with a filter using $5\ \mu\text{m}$ mesh size. As a third measure, the storage design was adapted. Ideally, a proper design that would allow a high level of ice slurry stratification would help to reduce ice particles pumped to the supercooler. In this regard, the first 150 l glass tank was replaced by a 1000 l intermediate bulk container (IBC). Having a bigger storage volume also leads to longer residence time of water in the tank and to lower velocities, both leading to a more stratified behavior of the ice-water mixture in the tank and thus reducing the likelihood to have ice in the outflow of the tank. With these measures, the preheating could be decreased to 1.05°C .

Figure 11: Picture of the opened ice storage tank, ice mesh and US level sensor. The temperature sensors TI-8-12 mentioned in 3.1 are submerged beneath the mesh.

3.1.5 Tank design: measurement of the produced ice amount

To quantify the amount of ice produced and stored in the vessel, the change of density measured by a water level sensor was used. This measurement technique needs that all ice is submerged in water, which was achieved using a cover plate that pushed the ice underwater. A perforated plate was used as structural cover,

combined with a stainless steel wire mesh and rubber sealing lips to ensure that no ice can bypass the mesh. An ultrasonic level sensor *Baumer UNAM 18U6903/S14* with a resolution of < 0.3 mm was used to determine the difference in water level. For constant water temperatures, the generated mass of ice can be calculated from the difference in level and densities:

$$m_{ice} = \frac{\rho_{wat} \cdot \rho_{ice}}{\rho_{wat} - \rho_{ice}} \Delta h A \quad (14)$$

where A is the base area of the tank, ρ_{wat} and ρ_{ice} (917 kg/m³) are the respective densities and Δh is the measured difference in height. The density of water however depends on its temperature, which influences the mass of ice during the heating phases. The average of all 5 tank temperature sensors were used as water temperature to determine its density. These sensors are located centered inside the tank, above each other. T1-12 (T-Wat-Tank-1) is positioned 5 cm from the bottom, the other temperature sensors are spaced with 15 cm distance in height between each other (compare with Fig. 11 and the description in section 3.1). The water density as a function of the temperature is calculated as:

$$\rho_{wat} = 7 \cdot 10^{-5} T_{wat}^3 - 0.0093 \cdot T_{wat}^2 + 0.0815 \cdot T_{wat} + 999.82 \quad (15)$$

where T_{wat} is the average water temperature in [°C] and ρ_{wat} the density of water. The mass of generated ice is then:

$$m_{ice} = (Ah - Ah_0 \frac{\rho_{w0}}{\rho_{wat}}) (\frac{\rho_{ice} \cdot \rho_{wat}}{\rho_{wat} - \rho_{ice}}) \quad (16)$$

with h the current tank filling level, h_0 the initial tank filling level and ρ_{w0} the water density at the start of ice production. The level measurements are 10-minute floating averages.

The power of the supercooler is calculated with:

$$\dot{Q}_{sc} = \Delta T_{sc} \cdot \dot{m}_{wat} \cdot c_{p,wat} \quad (17)$$

with ΔT_{sc} being the supercooling degree in [K], \dot{m}_{wat} the mass flow rate of water in [kg/s] and $c_{p,wat}$ is the heat capacity of water. Similarly, one can calculate the heat gains due to the mixer (mix) and barrier (bar):

$$\dot{Q}_{mix} = \Delta T_{mix} \dot{m}_{mix} c_{p,wat} \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{bar} = \Delta T_{bar} \dot{m}_{bar} c_{p,wat} \quad (19)$$

With the crystallization losses provoked by the thermal gains of the barrier and mixer, the efficiency of the efficiency of the ice crystallizer can be calculated:

$$\eta_{crys} = 1 - \frac{\dot{Q}_{bar} + \dot{Q}_{mix}}{\dot{Q}_{sc}} \quad (20)$$

Additionally, to calculate the difference between theoretical and measured ice production, the environmental heat gains from the ice storage and piping system $\dot{Q}_{env,tes}$ need to be accounted for. In overall, the heat gains that provoke the efficiency loss in ice production can be summarized as:

$$\dot{Q}_{\eta,loss} = \dot{Q}_{env,tes} + \dot{Q}_{bar} + \dot{Q}_{mix} \quad (21)$$

Thus, the overall efficiency of ice production of the system can be calculated as:

$$\eta_{ice} = 1 - \frac{\dot{Q}_{\eta,loss}}{\dot{Q}_{sc}} \quad (22)$$

3.1.6 Slurry tank inlet design

An even distribution of ice in the tank is important to maximize the storage capacity of the tank itself. Multiple tank inlet designs were manufactured and tested. The first slurry tank inlet design, shown in Fig. 12a, consists of a pipe reducer from d32 to d63 diameter followed by an elbow. The flow velocity is reduced by a factor of 4.5 due to this expansion. The opening of the elbow was tilted towards the tank wall (approx. by 45° with respect to the vertical) such that the slurry hits the storage wall first before it floats upwards. Nevertheless, the ice does not distribute uniformly into the tank: after covering the tank with a first ice layer, newly arriving ice interlocks with the already present one, resulting in a cone shape pointing towards the tank inlet. After arriving at the inlet, the accumulated ice crystals can block the inlet (after several hours of continuous slurry production). The second slurry tank inlet design shown in Fig. 12b divides the flow in three different directions that are each split in two horizontal pipes with size d40. This results in a much lower inlet velocity of 0.045 m/s and it was expected to spread the flow more evenly. This design was built horizontally. However, it suffered from blockage at the reducer of the *straight-through* exit, which actually leads to the development of the third tank inlet. The third slurry tank inlet design depicted in Fig. 12c was designed to minimize the chance of blockage in the narrow part of inlet 2 by simply removing this part. The dimensions however were increased to 40 mm for the first T-piece and to 50 mm for the four final inlet, resulting in a flow velocity of 0.042 m/s there. With this inlet shape, ice only rises due to buoyancy from the inlets because of the very low flow velocity, leading to higher uniformity of ice distribution in the tank. The horizontal design also consumes less space which increases the achievable *ice fraction* in the storage. However, flow velocities below 0.1 m/s are critical, as stated by [Kauffeld et al. \(2005\)](#). This requirement contradicts the tank inlet requirement for stratified tanks, which requires inlet flow velocities to be below 0.1 m/s ([Haller et al., 2015](#)). For large storage tanks, this stratification requirement can be substituted with requirements on the outlet velocities combined with the distance to the tank wall, as described by [Battaglia et al. \(2018\)](#). This should be considered while designing new tanks. Furthermore, it was found that tank inlets should not point towards the tank outlet, since this increases the chance of ice being fed through the tank towards the preheater. A larger amount of ice at the preheater requires more preheating energy and increases the chance of ice bypassing the preheater. The different tank inlets shown in Fig. 12a-d) have been tested at a main mass flow of 400 kg/h and a supercooling degree of 2 K. The runs using tank inlet 2 and 3 lead to blockage after 2 h to 6 h after initiation of ice production, either in the tank inlet itself, or due to the amount of ice fed into the tank outlet, leading to blockage of the supercooler. *STI 1* and *4* successfully operated for 24 h to 27 h. The amount of produced ice was of the same order of magnitude for the different inlets.

3.2 Experiments made with the presented setup

Before the slurry production is started the water in the storage is cooled down to a temperature close to zero degrees (normally 0°C to 0.15°C). The desired mass flow rate in the supercooled loop is achieved and the supercooling degree is adjusted followed by the activation of the ultrasonic (US) transducer (described in section 3.1.1). As soon as the first ice particles are visible in the mixer, the mixer pump is started, and the mixer valve is opened establishing the mixer flow. Consequently, the barrier is turned on by regulating the opening angle of a valve in order to prevent the upstream ice propagation (see section 3.1.2).

Figure 12: CAD drawings of three proposed tank inlet designs. a) Slurry tank inlet 1 (STI-1), side view: increases the pipe diameter to d_{63} , followed by an elbow. Ice and water leave towards the top of the tank. b) Slurry tank inlet 2 (STI-2), top view: a manifold splits the flow into three streams that are followed by T-pieces to reduce flow velocity. A reduction increases pressure drop in the "straight-through" exit to even out the mass flows in the three inlets. Water and ice leave this inlet horizontally. c) Slurry tank inlet 3 (STI-3): similar to slurry inlet 2, but with four 50 mm inlets instead of six 40 mm ones. d) (STI-4), side view: 90° elbow followed by a reducing T, increasing the pipe diameter from $d = 32$ mm to $d = 1$ mm.

3.2.1 Experimental campaign using the STI-1 inlet port

A series of experiments were carried out using the simplest functional pipe inlet design as shown in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: CAD drawing of the tank inlet designs. Slurry tank inlet 1 (STI-1), side view: increases the pipe diameter to D63, followed by an elbow. Ice and water leave towards the top of the tank.

Icing and natural melting

Experimental results for a continuous icing test with a main flow of 400 kg/h and a supercooling degree of 2 K are shown Fig. 14.

Figure 14: Experimental results for the 1 port inlet with a 90° bend (STI-1) as a function of time in hours. **top-left**: mass of ice; **top-right**: temperatures (left axis) at different parts of the system and pump power (right axis); **bottom-left**: temperatures inside the storage at different heights; **bottom-right**: mass flow rates. Icing with 2 K supercooling and natural melting.

The upper left plot shows the evolution of the mass of ice in the storage tank. A maximum mass of ice of 75 kg was measured after 27 h of continuous slurry production, resulting in an ice fraction of 23 % in the storage content². The mass of ice was obtained from the level sensor signal (as explained in section 3.1.5). The calculated values strongly depend on the accuracy of the level sensor. This sensor shows fluctuations in the range of ± 0.5 mm, resulting in the shown spread of almost ± 5 kg of ice. Fig. 14 (top,left) shows a linear ice production which means that the efficiency of the icing process does not depend on time. Contrary to

²We assume one third of our storage volume can't be filled with slurries due to the experimental set-up with a plastic led that separates slurry from pure water to be pumped.

typical ice-on-coil solution, ice does not grow on any heat transfer surface and therefore the efficiency of icing is not limited by the thermal resistance of the growing ice layer. This is an important benefit of ice production using the ice slurry supercooling method. It is important to state that a rather large ice amount was floating besides the PVC walls inside the tank and thus not pressed below the water level by the plate mounted to the storage (see Fig. 11). These plastic leads were not tight due to the expansion of the storage when filled with water. The ice that moves to the other side of the plastic wall floated on the surface since it could not be pressed below water. Thus, it does not contribute to the increase in water level measured by the sensor and is consequently neglected in the measurement.

The plot on the top-right of Fig. 14 shows the temperatures (left axis) at several places of the set-up and the pump power (right axis). The pump power behaviors can be used to assess which kind of fault the system had, i.e. where did it freeze. The relation between pump power and the fault-freeze is explained in section 3.3. On the freezing cycle it can be observed all the temperatures are very stable. On the natural melting process all the water sensors on the piping system increase to the ambient temperature of 25 °C.

The bottom left plot of Fig. 14 shows the tank temperatures during the icing and natural melting process from ambient heat gains. A temperature above 0 °C indicates that the ice around the sensor has been melted completely. This means that roughly at hour 60, the highest sensor $T_{\text{tnk},y=65\%}$ is free of ice. The melting of ice is clearly from bottom to top of the storage since warm water is injected at the bottom. Due to the lower density of ice compared to water, solid particles accumulate at the top and distribute following a conic shape towards the tank inlet. Since there is no forced convection, the tank develops a temperature stratification: warm water accumulates on the bottom of the tank, since water has a peak in density at a temperature of 4 °C. This stratification is kept until the water temperature increases locally above 4 °C when the warmer water starts to rise and mix with the layers above. The movement increases mixing of the water with the above layers until all the storage is fully mixed between 70 h and 75 h with an average temperature above 4 °C where all ice has been melted completely. After that, the temperature stratification change to the normal mode in sensible water storage where hot water is at the top.

Icing and forced melting

Experimental results for the melting process including several melting temperatures and mass flow rates used in the melting process are presented in this section.

Experimental results for a melting flow of 750 kg/h with a temperature of 10 °C are presented in Fig. 15. The ice content for this case increases until 60 kg where the pump power increases to a level that the ice detection mechanism turns off the system and an active melting process begins. In the melting process the barrier and mixer temperature are not representing any relevant value since there is not flow on them. The supercooler outlet temperature increases from -2 °C in the freezing process to the 10 °C in the melting process.

The melting process partly mixes the storage tank and is able to provide up to 9 kW at the beginning and reducing to around 6 kW after a short time dropping to 0 °C within 2 h. After some time at around 6 kW melting power, the capacity reduces to zero. A summary of the averaged experimental results are presented in Table 4 where the efficiency of the crystallizer calculated is 62 %.

Supercooling temperature	-2 °C
Main mass flow rate (icing)	400 kg/h
Barrier mass flow rate	28.7 kg/h
Mixer mass flow rate	812.5 kg/h
Ice mass flow rate after mixer	6.43 kg _{ice} /h
η_{crys}	62 %

Table 4: Summary results for the case on icing and forced melting with a melting mass flow rate of 750 kg/h and 10 °C.

Figure 15: Experimental results for the 1 port inlet with a 90° bend (STI-1) as a function of time in hours. **top-left**: mass ice fraction; **top-right**: temperatures (left axis) at different parts of the system and pump power (right axis); **bottom-left**: temperatures inside the storage at different heights; **bottom-right**: mass flow rates. Melting with water at 10 °C with a mass flow rate of 750 kg/h.

The following experiment presented in Fig. 16 were conducted for a melting mass flow rate of 2000 kg/h and a temperature of 10 °C. The melting power reaches 16 kW and quickly reduces to zero following the storage temperature, which is very well mixed despite the fact the both inlet and outlet of the storage at the bottom.

Figure 16: Experimental results for the 1 port inlet with a 90° bend (STI-1) as a function of time in hours. **top-left:** mass ice fraction; **top-right:** temperatures (left axis) at different parts of the system and pump power (right axis); **bottom-left:** temperatures inside the storage at different heights; **bottom-right:** mass flow rates. Melting with water at 10 °C with a mass flow rate of 2000 kg/h.

Figure 17: Experimental results for the 1 port inlet with a 90° bend (STI-1) as a function of time in hours. **top-left:** mass ice fraction; **top-right:** temperatures (left axis) at different parts of the system and pump power (right axis); **bottom-left:** temperatures inside the storage at different heights; **bottom-right:** mass flow rates. Melting with water at 20 °C with a mass flow rate of 400 kg/h.

Figure 18: Experimental results for the 1 port inlet with a 90° bend (STI-1) as a function of time in hours. **top-left:** mass ice fraction; **top-right:** temperatures (left axis) at different parts of the system and pump power (right axis); **bottom-left:** temperatures inside the storage at different heights; **bottom-right:** mass flow rates. Melting with water at 20 °C with a mass flow rate of 2000 kg/h.

3.2.2 Experimental campaign using the STI-4 inlet port

A series of experiments were carried out using a variation of a simple tee-piece with a 90° bend upwards as shown in Fig. 19.

Figure 19: CAD drawing of the tank inlet designs. Slurry tank inlet 4 (STI-4), side view: 90° elbow followed by a tee-piece increasing the pipe diameter.

Figure 20: Experimental results for the tee-piece port inlet with a 90° upward bend (STI-4) as a function of time in hours. **top-left:** mass ice fraction; **top-right:** temperatures (left axis) at different parts of the system and pump power (right axis); **bottom-left:** temperatures inside the storage at different heights; **bottom-right:** mass flow rates.

3.2.3 Experimental campaign using the tee-piece inlet port

A series of experiments were carried out using a variation of a simple tee-piece as shown in Fig. 21. Results for this inlet port are provided in Fig. 22. The maximum ice production does not increase compared to the simple STI-1 inlet port. However, from the results shown in Fig. 22 it is not possible to see a sign of failure, which means that the experiment was probably stop manually. Thus, from these results it is not possible to assess if this configuration would improve the ice packing factor.

Figure 21: CAD drawing of the tank inlet designs. Slurry tank inlet 4 (STI-4).

Figure 22: Experimental results for the tee-piece port inlet as a function of time in hours. **top-left:** mass ice fraction; **top-right:** temperatures (left axis) at different parts of the system and pump power (right axis); **bottom-left:** temperatures inside the storage at different heights; **bottom-right:** mass flow rates.

3.2.4 Experimental campaign using the 3-Y inlet port

A series of experiments were carried out using a design using 3-Y pieces, as shown in Fig. 23. The 3-Y inlet port was working reliably, but the maximum solid fraction was not increased respect to the previous designs. However, from the results presented in Fig.23 one can be seen that the freezing event was not due to the inlet port, but to a fast freezing event, e.g. supercooler freezing. Unfortunately, this was not realized at the time of conducting the experiments and no more experiments were conducted. Thus, with the current data, we cannot assess whether this design could improve the maximum solid ice fraction or not.

Figure 23: CAD drawing of the tank inlet designs. Slurry tank inlet 4 (STI-4).

Figure 24: Experimental results for the tee-piece port inlet as a function of time in hours. **top-left:** mass ice fraction; **top-right:** temperatures (left axis) at different parts of the system and pump power (right axis); **bottom-left:** temperatures inside the storage at different heights; **bottom-right:** mass flow rates.

3.2.5 Experimental campaign using the second generation of jet mixer

The mixer used in the experiments presented in section 3.2 works reliable only with a high enough temperature of the injected water ($\geq 0.3^\circ\text{C}$) and with a high mass flow rate in the mixer inlets (double the supercooled main flow). Both aspects reduce the power of the crystallizer due to the big heat gains. In order to reduce heat gains increasing thus crystallization power a second generation of jet mixer was developed. According to different references (Hatch et al., 1992, Holdeman, 1991, Obispo, 2012), the mixing capability of a jet mixer is dependent on the ratio of the momentum flux of the jets and the main flow. If the mass flow rate of jets and the main flow is in the same order of magnitude, the mixing quality is dependent on the ratio of jet and main flow velocity v_{jet}/v_{main} . To increase the velocity of the jet flow, the second design of the jet mixer uses very small orifices of two different types. Type A orifices are tangential round holes with a diameter of 1.5 mm which are designed to force the main mass flow to a rotational motion. Type B orifices are slanted slots with a length of 3-4 mm and a width of 1.5 mm tilted with an angle of 45° with respect to the main flow direction (see Fig. 25 D). The idea of Type B is to enhance the penetration depth of the jets as well as the swirl component and the circumferential mixing.

A

Figure 25: CAD drawings of the jet mixer A) full assembly of the jet mixer. B) Zoom to the inlet side of the jet mixer with tangential jet inlets marked red (type A) and slanted slot jet inlets marked black (type B). C) Zoom to the outlet, color code as in B). D) Dimensions of slanted slots (orifices type B).

The second generation jet mixer is designed with a double pipe, where the inner one ($d_i = 59.2\text{ mm}$) contains the main flow and the outer one ($d_i = 105.6\text{ mm}$) serves for the injection of the jet flows. The connection between the 32 mm inlet pipe, where the ice is growing to the inner mixer pipe, is realized by a standard reduction piece (as well used for the connection between inner mixer pipe and outlet pipe). The mixer is constructed in such a way that access to the inner pipe, e.g. for changing amount and position of orifices, is guaranteed and realizable without destroying the mixer. This is achieved using flange and threaded connections instead of only glued joints (see Fig. 25 A - C). Several "rings" of six orifices each equally distributed were drilled into the inner pipe with a distance of 120 mm between the rings and alternating orifice type A and B. Additionally, both reductions (at in- and outlet) host a ring of six orifices of type A (tangential) to support

circular motion in the reductions and to prevent blocking in these places. The total length of the inner pipe is 1200 mm.

Figure 26: Photograph of the jet mixer with mounted barrier and ultrasonic device upstream to the jet mixer.

Successful test runs over 30 min could be executed for a main mass flow rate of 1000 kg/h at a supercooling degree of 2.0 K with a supercooling power of 2.1 kW where the mass flow rate of jet was 960 kg/h. This results in a mass flow ratio of main to jet of 1:1 (instead of 1:2 used with the previous mixing device). The temperature of the jets was $\approx 0.3^\circ\text{C}$ (not measured but tubing and pump for mixer bypass similar to setup before), resulting in a mixer heat gains of 0.33 kW. The operating values for the barrier for the higher main mass flow rate had to be increased to a mass flow rate of 66 kg/h at a temperature of 3.8°C , resulting in a crystallization loss of 0.27 kW. Consequently, the remaining power of the crystallizer using the 2nd generation jet mixer was 1.5 kW.

Furthermore the crystallizer could be operated at a main mass flow rate of 1250 kg/h at a supercooling degree of 1.75 K for 20 minutes reaching a crystallization power of 1.78 kW. After this time, the supercooler was blocked due to a failure of the barrier. which means that the mixing device could most likely be operated for a longer time. The resulting crystallizer power and heat gains for this test run are listed in Table 5.

Supercooling temperature	-1.75 °C
Main mass flow rate (icing)	1250 kg/h
Supercooling power	2.3 kW
Barrier mass flow rate	70 kg/h
Barrier temperature	3 °C
Barrier thermal gains	0.22 kW
Mixer mass flow rate	960 kg/h
Mixer temp. estimated	0.3 °C
Mixer thermal gains	0.3 kW
Crystallizer power	1.78 kW
η_{crys}	77 %

Table 5: Summary of power and losses for second generation jet mixer operated at a main mass flow of 1250 kg/h at a supercooling degree of 1.75°C .

The following main reasons for failure of the crystallizer including the 2nd generation jet mixer were observed:

1. **Failure of the barrier:** The designed barrier presented in section 3.1.2 did not work for the higher main mass flow rate of 1000 kg/h resp. 1250 kg/h, i.e. ice is able to grow back into the supercooler.
2. **Ice at the orifices for jet inlets:** Due to production methods it is difficult to avoid splinters and deformation around the orifices in the inner pipe that facilitate ice growth at the jet inlets.

3. **Ice forming between inner and outer pipe:** Some nucleation trials using ultrasound ended up with ice crystals between the inner and the outer tube of the jet mixer but no crystals in the inner pipe. This was observed solely after a long period of flowing supercooled water through the system without triggering of nucleation. As a consequence, the (almost standing) water between outer and inner tube seems to get supercooled (no temperature sensor there). If the jet mixer design should be further developed it might be helpful to reduce the volume of the (almost) standing water in the outer pipe.

3.3 Fault analysis

In this project, an entire system made of multiple components has been built and tested. Failure can originate from various locations in the system and sometimes it is not enough to find out where the problem originated. The most reliable fault analysis used is observation by eye, which is possible thanks to the transparent piping. However, for long test icing the storage vessel, it is not always possible to be present in the lab when a freezing event occurs. Thus, understanding the patterns of the most frequent faults and their influences on the system is very important.

3.3.1 Blockage in the supercooler

Ice freezing inside the supercooler can have several reasons. A supercooling degree which is large enough to induce spontaneous nucleation is the most frequent one. It may origin from increased cooling on the chiller side, from low-flow conditions in the water loop or simply by the stochastic nature of freezing. Moreover, freezing in the supercooler might also come from impurities on the water flow or by the presence of small ice particles acting as nucleation sites. There is one temperature sensor at the inlet and outlet of the supercooler that can be used for the fault analysis, as well as the main pump rate. Experimental results of such an event can be seen in Figure 27 where the mass flow rates are shown on the left and temperature and pump power on the right. for the fault analysis the time scale resolution used is in seconds.

The main indicators of a frozen supercooler are:

- **Short and steep increase of the pump rate.** This is arguably the strongest indicator for a frozen supercooler. Since the supercooler is the coldest point in the entire system, freezing speed is the fastest. The distance between the heat exchanger plates is narrow and easily filled with ice which can not be flushed away. The PID flow controller aims to stabilize the flow at the given mass flow set point despite the blocked channels, which quickly increases the pump rate. Due to the no-flow condition at the blocked channels, their temperature is further reduced, increasing freezing speed. Thus, a freezing event can be determined by the sudden decrease of mass flow rate (red line on left plot from Fig. 27) and increase of pump power (black dots on right plot of Fig. 27).
- **Temperature drop at the supercooler outlet.** When the supercooler is freezing, the outlet water temperature (orange line on right plot of Fig. 27), which is the coldest of the system, tends to increase quickly due to the latent heat release. Since the mass flow on the water side is reduced, the heat transfer between glycol and water is reduced and the glycol outlet temperature decreases.

Figure 27: Experimental results showing a typical supercooling freezing event.

3.3.2 Failure of the barrier

A low barrier volume flow, a low temperature of the introduced barrier flow, or a misaligned barrier, i.e. incoming and outgoing pipe in the barrier are not aligned properly in axial direction (see Figure 8) may allow ice to travel across the barrier towards the direction of the supercooler. It propagates along the pipe walls towards the next position where it can not be flushed away anymore. This is usually an elbow or a fitting. It can be detected using the surface sensor placed on the pipe between the supercooler and the barrier. Ice grows on the inside of the pipe wall leading to an increase in temperature at this position prior to blockage with a rapid decrease of the barrier temperature sensor which gets frozen too. This freezing event can be observed in Fig. 28. The blockage itself leads to a behavior similar to a frozen supercooler, but here the supercooler outlet freezes immediately (around 1 second) while when the freezing originates inside the supercooler the freezing takes about 10 seconds. Moreover, the barrier temperature in a frozen supercooler does not show a decrease as sharp as here.

Figure 28: An experimental result showing a typical upstream prevention barrier freezing event.

Another example of a barrier frozen is shown in Fig. 29. On the right plot we see an almost exact behavior of the supercooling freezing event. However, if we zoom out as shown in the left plot as Fig. 29 we can observe that at around 550 seconds, the $T_{wat,surf}$ sensor (placed between the barrier and the supercooler) starts to slightly increase its temperature over time. We can also observe the the drop of temperature at the barrier is faster in this experiment compared to the supercooling freezing event. Understanding these little details are very important to isolate problems and improve the different sections of the crystallizer design.

Figure 29: An experimental results showing a typical upstream prevention barrier freezing event which is very similar to a supercooler freezing.

3.3.3 Failure of the mixer

A low mixer volume flow or low temperature of the mixed water can lead to blockage in the mixer itself or downstream the flow. For example, at mixer outlet sensor or anywhere on the fittings mounted downstream the mixer. This is either because the supercooling degree is not released completely inside the crystallizer mixing device or because ice agglomerated within an obstacle. Typical behaviors of sensor data during a failure of the mixer are shown in Fig. 30 and characteristic indicators of this cause of fault are listed below.

- **A non-fluctuating constant temperature at 0° at mixer outlet sensor.** Ice growing on the surface of the temperature sensor immersed at the outlet of the mixer can be detected by a flat line at 0 °C in the measured data. Before the freezing event initiates, the sensor temperature fluctuates around zero indicating that the supercooling of the flow is completely released, but at certain point (clearly visible in Figure 30 at time 2600 s) the sensor measures exactly 0 °C without any fluctuation at the time when the pump power starts to increase exponentially.
- **Slow increase in pump rate.** If the mixer fails the pump rate usually increases over more than 15 minutes before blockage of the system. This freezing event can be either due to the freezing of an already low supercooled water or by the ice particle agglomeration.
- **Decrease in mixer volume flow (Figure 30 b) blue line).** Shortly after the first visible sign of a mixer failure in the pump power signal a decrease in the mixer mass flow can be observed. As the blockage caused by the mixer occurs after the barrier, the barrier mass flow is barely affected.

Figure 30: Experimental results showing a typical mixer freezing event. Pump power increases exponentially. At the same time, the mixer outlet temperature sensor is covered in ice, detectable by showing a constant value of 0 °C. Soon after, the mass flow of the mixer starts to drop, until the entire set-up is shut off automatically at 1 h.

3.3.4 Failure of the tank inlet

Elevated amounts of ice within the storage tank tend to grow towards the tank inlet. As soon as the tank inlet is reached, ice is being pushed away from the inlet by the incoming water mass. This process repeats itself, compressing and pushing away the growing mass of ice. It can be detected best by a pulsing behavior of the pump rate (visible in Figure 31 a). The remaining sensors show a behavior comparable to a blockage in the supercooler.

Figure 31: Sensor values during failure due to ice reaching the tank inlet. The pump speed fluctuates already from 14 h onwards, but always reaches the base level of 6.5 % again. The mass flows and temperatures are largely unaffected. The run was manually stopped at 23.30 h: all pumps were stopped at this time, which explains the full stop of all flows.

3.3.5 Failure of the preheater

This cause of failure is the most difficult one to distinguish, since the effective blockage occurs in the supercooler and the sensor values are almost identical to a failure of the supercooler. The only difference is an insufficient temperature at the supercooler water inlet (T_{I-5}) due to low temperature or flow conditions in the preheater loop (loop iii) in Figure 6). However, the required flow and temperature depends on the main mass flow and the amount of ice that is suck into the loop from the storage. A temperature of 1.05° at the supercooler inlet was found to be sufficient for most operating conditions.

4 Ice storage modeling and validation

The formulation of the ice storage model is based on the mass and energy conservation laws. The ice storage is assumed to have direct connections that are used as heat and mass transfer inlet/outlet ports. Therefore, these ports can bring liquid water at a certain temperature or a mixture of solid and liquid water. The total amount of mass inside the storage, either liquid water or the mixture of solid and liquid water, is constant.

The conservation of mass inside the ice-slurry storage reads:

$$m_{total} = m_s + m_l \quad (23)$$

where m_{total} is the total mass of water filled into the storage and the subscripts s and l stand for solid (ice) and liquid (water) phases respectively.

Since the total mass of water (liquid and solid) is known by the volume of the storage and density of the filled water, it is only necessary to calculate the change of solid mass per time (kg/s) as:

$$\frac{dm_s}{dt} = \sum_{n=1}^n \Delta \dot{m}_{s,n} + \alpha_{s,l} A_{s,l} \frac{(T_s - T_l)}{h_f} \quad (24)$$

where $\Delta \dot{m}_s$ represents the change of solid mass in kg/s between the inlet ($m_{s,in}$) and outlet ($m_{s,out}$) of each direct port n , and the subscripts s and l stand for solid (ice) and liquid (water) respectively. The second term of the right hand side represents the melted solid due to the warmer liquid temperature T_l respect to the solid temperature T_s . This terms depends on an overall heat transfer coefficient $\alpha_{s,l}$ and the contact area between solid and liquid $A_{s,l}$.

It is assumed that no supercooled liquid enters the ice slurry storage. The ice crystallizer is in charge to convert the supercooled water into an ice slurry and it is assumed that the bulk temperature of the ice slurry flow is at 0 °C (all supercooling potential has been converted into solid). The conversion of the supercooled water into an slurry flow is given by Eq 11 in terms of percentage of the main water flow. The total mass of ice that enters the ice slurry tank can be calculated using the ice packing factor of the flow IPF_{flow} as:

$$\dot{m}_{s,in} = IPF_{flow} \dot{m}_{flow} \quad (25)$$

We assume that no slurry is pumped to the outlet and therefore $\dot{m}_{s,out} = 0$. The total mass of liquid water that enters the ice slurry tank can be calculated as:

$$\dot{m}_{l,in} = (1 - IPF_{flow}) \dot{m}_{flow} \quad (26)$$

and we assume that only liquid water is pumped to the outlet:

$$\dot{m}_{l,out} = \dot{m}_{s,in} + \dot{m}_{l,in} \quad (27)$$

The energy conservation low is formulated assuming a zero dimensional model with only one control volume for the whole storage where the solid and liquid parts are separated by density gradients (no stirring device). The energy conservation is applied to the water of the storage since the ice is always at 0 °C. Notice that it is not possible to cool solid ice below 0 °C with the supercooling slurry production technology.

The energy equation for the ice slurry tank reads:

$$\dot{Q}_{accum,l} = \sum_{n=1}^n \dot{Q}_n + \dot{Q}_{lat} - \dot{Q}_{env} \quad (28)$$

where $\dot{Q}_{accum,l}$ represents the cumulative sensible heat term of liquid water in W, \dot{Q}_n the heat provided via the n direct port, \dot{Q}_{lat} is the latent heat release and \dot{Q}_{env} represents the heat exchanged with the surrounding environment.

The accumulative sensible heat of liquid water is calculated as:

$$Q_{accum,l} = m_l c_p \frac{dT_l}{dt} \quad (29)$$

where c_p is the specific heat capacity of liquid water and m_l is the mass of liquid water in the storage in kg, T_l the average liquid water temperature and t the time.

The term \dot{Q}_{lat} includes the change in energy due to the melting or solidification of ice:

$$\dot{Q}_{lat} = h_f \frac{dm_s}{dt} \quad (30)$$

where h_f the enthalpy of fusion and m_s the mass of ice. With these assumptions, the energy equation reads:

$$m_l c_p \frac{dT_l}{dt} = h_f \frac{dm_s}{dt} + \dot{Q}_{env} + \sum_{n=1}^n \dot{Q}_n \quad (31)$$

Discretizing over time Eq. 31 reads:

$$m_l c_p \frac{T_l - T_l^0}{\Delta t} = h_f \frac{m_s - m_s^0}{\Delta t} + \dot{Q}_{env} + \sum_{n=1}^n \dot{Q}_n \quad (32)$$

where Δt is the time step and the superscript 0 refers to values of the previous time step. We use an implicit scheme in which Eq. 32 solves the temperatures and mass of ice of the current time step.

The energy exchanged with the direct ports Q_n can be calculated as:

$$Q_n = c_p (\dot{m}_{l,in} T_{in} - \dot{m}_{l,out} T_{out}) \quad (33)$$

The heat exchanged with the environment is calculated assuming a constant heat transfer coefficient U_{env} as:

$$\dot{Q}_{env} = U_{env} \cdot A_{env} \cdot (T_l - T_{env}) \quad (34)$$

where A_{env} is the surface area of the storage tank and T_{env} is the temperature of the environment, which in the present case can be the ground or cellar temperature depending on the placement of the storage. The heat loss coefficient is provided as an input of the model for several surfaces, i.e. top, bottom and lateral sides.

4.1 Validation of the ice slurry model

The experimental results presented in section 3 have been used here to validate the ice slurry model. The main reason to develop an ice slurry mode is to be able to use it in dynamic yearly simulations while being integrated in complete energy systems. For integrating the model in a system simulation framework we have implemented the model in TRNSYS using Fortran 90 language.

The first validation step provided in section 4.1.1 consist on determining the overall heat transfer coefficient between the ice storage and the environment U_{env} . For this purposes a natural heating process is used. The second step is to determinate the heat transfer coefficient between solid and liquid in a natural convection process $\alpha_{s,l}$. This is provided in section 4.1.2. Afterwards, the heat transfer coefficient between the solid and the liquid phase is estimated for a forced convection melting process in section 4.1.3.

4.1.1 Natural heating

An experiment was conducted by cooling down the storage to 0°C and stopping the mass flow rate flowing through the storage completely. Therefore, the ice storage was heated by the heat gains from ambient air by natural convection. Numerical and experimental results are shown in Fig. 32 where the model has shown to predict the experimental results very well. For that the U_{env} of 35 W/(m²K) has been used and kept constant for all other simulations.

Figure 32: Numerical and experimental results for a natural heating process.

4.1.2 Natural melting

An experiment was conducted by icing the slurry storage and stopping the mass flow rate flowing through the storage completely. Afterwards, the ice was melted by natural convection through the gains from the ambient air. Numerical and experimental results are shown in Fig. 33 where the average liquid temperature of the storage is shown on the left and the mass of ice on the right.

For the natural melting process, besides knowing the U_{env} value we need the contact area between solid and liquid $A_{s,l}$ and the heat transfer coefficient $\alpha_{s,l}$. The contact area between solid and liquid is relatively difficult to calculate and a highly simplified approach has been used for the current model. The solid fraction is assumed to be a monolithic block floating in the liquid water with a 5 cm wide gap between the solid block and the tank wall filled with liquid as suggested by [Tamasauskas et al. \(2012\)](#). Since the gap between solid and wall and the shape of the assumption of the solid forming a *block* is rather arbitrary the $\alpha_{s,l}$ was calibrated with the experiments instead of trying to find a physical model adjusted by a non realistic contact area. A value of $500 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K})$ was used to achieve the results presented in Fig. 33. In future, a more physically based approach will be used for the solid to liquid contact area and the heat transfer will be calculated accordingly.

The average liquid temperature deviates in this case because the storage is stratified since it is not submitted to a forced flow. The model is zero dimensional and therefore assumed that all the storage is fully mixed. Nevertheless, for this particular case the most important is to predict properly the mass of melted ice which is reasonably well predicted.

Figure 33: Numerical and experimental results for an icing process followed by natural melting.

4.1.3 Icing and forced convection

Hereafter, the most important experiments are presented for icing and forced melting. Icing is provided by injecting solid mass into the storage via the direct port and afterwards a forced melting is analyzed using different mass flow rates and temperatures to assess if the model properly captures those differences.

Fig. 34 shows the results for a melting case with a temperature of 10 °C and a \dot{m}_{flow} of 2000 kg/h. It can be observed that for this case both average liquid temperature of the storage and mass of ice are properly predicted. Clearly, in this case with a high mass flowing through the storage, the temperatures of the liquid water are fully mixed. In the case of forced convection the heat transfer from liquid to solid $\alpha_{s,l}$ has been set to 10 000 W/(m²K). This value is rather high, but in practice, the contact area between ice and liquid water is likely to be significantly higher compared to the assumption of a monolithic block due to the water flowing through the ice particles.

Figure 34: Numerical and experimental results for an icing process followed by forced melting with a mass flow of 2000 kg/h and a temperature of 10 °C.

Fig. 35 shows the same case as Fig. 34, but reducing the mass flow rate for melting from 2000 kg/h to 750 kg/h. Keeping the same value of $\alpha_{s,l}$ of 1000 W/(m²K) the predictions follow the experiments accurately. Actually the melting process is better predicted with 750 kg/h compared to using 2000 kg/h using the same value of $\alpha_{s,l}$. Since it is not convenient to calibrate the $\alpha_{s,l}$ for different mass flow rates, a constant value that provides reasonable results in the whole tested range has been chosen.

Figure 35: Numerical and experimental results for an icing process followed by forced melting with a mass flow of 750 kg/h and a temperature of 10 °C.

Two more experiments are used for the validation where the melting temperature was increased to 20 °C. Fig. 36 shows the results for a melting case with a temperature of 20 °C and a \dot{m}_{flow} of 2000 kg/h. The predicted melting process is slightly slower than in reality, which is reasonable since the melting process using a constant $\alpha_{s,l}$ works well for lower mass flow rates and in this case the turbulence will enhance heat transfer. Nevertheless, predictions are in a good agreement with experiments for yearly transient simulations purposes.

Figure 36: Numerical and experimental results for an icing process followed by forced melting with a mass flow of 2000 kg/h and a temperature of 20 °C.

The last case considered is the same as shown in Fig. 36 but decreasing the melting mass flow rate from 2000 kg/h to 400 kg/h. For this case also the melting process seems to be slightly better predicted compared to the high mass flow rate case.

In summary, the ice slurry storage model has been compared with experimental results to validate the model. The assumption of a fully mixed storage is relatively good for icing and forced melting, which are the most important situation we need to deal with in yearly transient simulations. This model was successfully implemented in the open source pytrnsys environment (TRNSYS based) and used for hundreds of simulations that were presented within the H2020 TRI-HP project in [Gurruchaga et al. \(2023a\)](#).

Figure 37: Numerical and experimental results for an icing process followed by forced melting with a mass flow of 400 kg/h and a temperature of 20 °C.

5 Conclusions

Supercooling of water for ice slurry production is a challenging technology that has not yet been deployed in Europe despite the fact that it has had a long history of development in Japan. The technology readiness level (TRL) in Europe is some steps behind that of Japan in this field, but since the know-how in Japan is proprietary to private sector entities, it is difficult to use the existing literature to solve the challenges we face on the technology development. Although Europe has been behind Japan in several respects, we are producing innovations to the foundational Japanese systems by using icephobic coatings that have been proven to work very efficiently even in very compact, brazed heat exchangers commonly used with conventional residential heat pumps that are subject to highly turbulent flows. We have contributed a key innovation in the application of ice slurries with supercooling method for residential heating applications using what is known as "solar-ice" slurry. In [Carbonell et al. \(2017b, 2020\)](#) we suggested for the first time the application of the "supercooling ice slurry" method for solar-ice applications. In a H2020 project called TRI-HP (www.tri-hp.eu), we developed and demonstrated in the laboratory, for the first time worldwide, the concept for ice slurry supercooling in solar-ice systems. This was possible thanks to the developed icephobic coatings that were demonstrated to work very effectively in supercoolers ([Carbonell et al., 2022](#)). The current project Slurry-Store must to be included in this context of continuous development of the ice slurry technology using the supercooling method. The supercoolers developed in TRI-HP were used in the present project to generate supercooled water.

In the Slurry-Store project, a method to produce ice from pure supercooled water in a closed, continuously operating system was conceived, designed, fabricated and tested. The entire ice slurry system consisted of an ice slurry storage tank, a pump to convey the supercooled liquid water and subsequently generated slurry, a preheater, in line filter and a static mixer to remove remaining solid impurities and ice crystals in the tank outlet; a supercooling heat exchanger ("supercooler") and a flow-based crystallizer that is responsible for converting the supercooled water into a fluidized ice slurry. Most of these parts have been adapted and adjusted over multiple iterations.

In a first design, a continuous production of ice for more than 24 hours and up to 70 kg of ice was demonstrated, resulting in a solid mass fraction (*ice packing factor*) of 12 % in the storage tank, a crystallizer efficiency of 60 % and a crystallizer power of 560 W. Using the second generation of jet mixers in the crystallizer resulted in increasing the crystallization power up to 1700 W with a crystallization efficiency of 77 %. In the second experimental campaign, the bottle neck was the thermal break. Resolving this limitation, it is conceivable that the current jet mixer would allow for higher crystallization power output.

The current state of knowledge of the flow-based crystallizer for supercooled water includes the identification of individual strategies that are effective to inhibit upstream ice propagation, initiate controlled nucleation, and

promote ice-slurry fluidization post-crystallizer. Thus, the overall concept incorporates three components that are strongly interdependent. A failure in one of the three components results in breakdown of the overall ice slurry process, making it essential that all three components are treated cohesively as a single mechanism. This unit must ensure a complete consumption/release of the supercooling potential to produce pumpable ice slurry. The required residence time within this device and thereby its volume can be reduced by increasing the internal rates of heat and mass transfer (via turbulent mixing) and by increasing the population of available nuclei to propagate crystallization. However, more research is needed to further reduce the flow-based crystallizer's energy consumption (i.e., internal heat gains reducing nucleation yield), increase the thermal power from crystallization and enhance its tolerance to varied operation conditions.

It was shown that the complete system was able to supercool water by more than 3 K for short duration and by 2 K in steady state for more than 24 hours while producing ice slurry when all the devices and components that have been described herein are present and functioning. It was found that supercooling operation at 3 K challenged the stable operation of the flow-based ice crystallizer system rather than the supercooler.

Multiple tank inlet configurations have been evaluated with the aim to increase the ice packing factor and improve 2-phase stratification in the ice storage tank. Also, methods have been tested to limit entrained ice crystals in the piping from the tank to the supercooler. For very low fluid flow velocities, the slurries stratify at the top of the piping system. Thus, classical tank stratification guideline using low fluid velocities at the the port inlet can not be used here due to contradicting ice slurry transportation limitations. Furthermore, tank inlets should be placed in such a way that ice is pushed away from tank outlets to prevent ice from re-entering the closed loop circulation of water. The throw distance, a ratio of outlet velocity and the distance to the next tank wall should be strongly considered during tank design.

Different approaches to melt the ice stored in the tank via direct contact heat exchange have been tested, using flow rates between 400 kg/h to 2000 kg/h resulting in peak melting powers ranging from 8 kW to 14 kW. Flow velocities, inlet, outlet and water temperatures at five different heights within the tank were measured during melting. This data was used to successfully validate an ice slurry storage numerical model.

5.1 Next steps

Within the current SFOE project Slurry-Store, we have been able to demonstrate that stable conditions exist to yield continuous supercooling and crystallization for long periods of time. However, at the proposal stage of Slurry-Store, we were not aware of all of the challenges we would encounter to develop an effective and reliable flow-based crystallizer. In particular, a controlled crystallization process is challenging within a supercooled flow, since as soon as one ice particle is generated within the system, the supercooled flow is likely to freeze throughout the entire flow stream unless using a thoroughly designed crystallizer.

We have tested several designs and succeeded in producing a stable crystallization process. However, the heat gains within the crystallizer were significant, and the power achieved was too far diminished for a proper scale-up. Our approach until now has been based on trial and error, and we have gained a lot of know-how from experimental evidence of what can or cannot work. Moreover, we have conceived new concepts of what could work or improve based on the knowledge acquired in this project, but fabricating many specific designs with small variants to intimately learn how some system parameters affect others would be too time consuming. Therefore, without a complete understanding and the capability to predict the physical phenomena involved in the process, it is challenging to confidently propose a design for an efficient and scalable crystallizer. Thus, the necessary next step is to develop a numerical model able to consider the main characteristics and governing processes of the crystallization problem. Following this approach, a new project called ModIceCrys, also funded by SFOE, will be used to develop a numerical tool that supports the design and the scale-up of flow-based ice crystallizers.

It is also important we design a method that does not require additional heat input to the crystallizer. The main reason is that while "waste/free" heat can be easily sourced in cooling applications from ambient temperature heat sinks, it is not readily available and thus not free in heating applications. For heating applications, heat sources above 0 °C can be readily utilized used to melt the ice instead of making the crystallizer work. However, for heating applications, such a readily available ambient heat sink to supply the thermal break to

the crystallizer is not possible, and would therefore require the consumption of primary energy to supply the thermal break. Ideally, the use of a thermal break for heating applications could be avoided. A project currently underway that is financed by the Department of Energy (DOE) from the United States of America (USA) together with the company Echogen is expected to provide a step forward in the experimental development of the crystallizer that together with the new project ModIceCrys are expected to bring this technology one step further.

Despite the work conducted on the ice slurry storage vessel, work remains to be done to confidently design a storage concept capable of containing elevated ice fractions while also eliminating ice entrainment to the supercooler and avoiding blockages to the slurry entrance port to the vessel. Introducing the slurries from the top is likely to improve the ice packing factor, but other unforeseen challenges might be faced and a project is necessary to experimentally assess new storage designs. Moreover, we foresee a future cost advantage in using existing spaces/rooms in buildings for storing ice slurries. Thus, a deep know-how will be necessary to fill any vessel shape with enough ice slurry content and manage the challenges for both the vessel inlet and outlet ports. In this context, a suitable 2-phase separation technology between solid and liquid water is also very important in order to minimize the risk of pumping ice particles into the supercooler. As mentioned before, the typical approach of preheating water above 0 °C is more limiting in heating applications since preheating is not for free as it would be in cooling applications.

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